

Addressing Trauma in Prisons:

The Potential for Trauma-Informed Practice to Reduce Re-Traumatisation.

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Abstract

Trauma exposure amongst the prison population is extremely high, with research finding over 80% of prisoners report experiencing at least one adverse childhood experience (Ford et al., 2020). In comparison, research in the general population finds just under half of participants report experiencing no adversities in their childhood (Witt et al., 2019). Inside the prison environment, which is described to be dangerously depriving (Haney, 2012), trauma can manifest itself in behaviours that many label as 'maladaptive' (Armour, 2012). Adopting a critical literature review, this research thematically found these behaviours include but are not limited to: mental health, drug use, self-harm, self-inflicted deaths, and inmate-on-inmate assaults. Such behaviour appears to be extremely high, for example almost 70% of incarcerated women felt their mental health had worsened during their time in prison (Augsburger et al., 2022). This is consistent with the combined model, which contends the prison environment can exacerbate imported experiences of trauma in the depriving prison environment (Dye, 2010). The implementation of trauma-informed practices in prisons is assessed to determine whether they can prevent re-traumatising people in prison. Using an array of research, including findings from Massachusetts Correctional Institution Framingham, this research finds trauma-informed practices have the potential to perform very successfully, but not without radical change (Benedict and CORE Associates, 2014; Levenson and Willis, 2018). This research suggests this radical change must focus on funding, leadership, staff turnover, and overcrowding in order for trauma-informed practices to succeed in preventing re-traumatising those who live and work inside prisons (Uglean, 2024; Jewkes et al., 2019).

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

This research will use trauma theory to highlight the weight that trauma exposure can hold on individuals; exposure in childhood can have disadvantageous effects on their physiological, emotional, cognitive, and social function (Heide and Solomon, 2006). Using trauma theory as the basis of knowledge, this research will explore how trauma exposure can manifest in behaviours of those in prison. Using Syke's pains of imprisonment (POI), the deprivation, imported, and combined models, this research will discuss whether this behaviour is the product of: an oppressive prison environment, pre-existing individual characteristics, or a combination of both factors (Cao et al., 1997; DeLisi et al., 2004). Acknowledging this, trauma-informed practices (TIPs) are assessed to determine whether they are the solution to prevent re-traumatisation. This assessment will use recommendations from Farmer's (2019) review and The Female Offender Strategy (Ministry of Justice, 2018) and the success of Massachusetts Correctional Institution (MCI) Framingham (Benedict and CORE Associates, 2014), while also acknowledging that the current implementation is not working, and what could be done to prevent this (Chief Inspector of Prisons, 2025; Kelman et al., 2024b; Hardan et al., 2023).

1.2 Research questions, aim and objectives

The overarching question of this research is: can trauma-informed practices reduce the re-traumatisation of people in the prison environment? The underpinning research questions are specific to each of the core chapters: chapter two considers how does trauma manifest within prison violence and harm; chapter three considers to what extent can trauma-informed practices enhance support for prisoners and staff?

This research aims to explore how trauma manifests in the prison population, assessing whether implementing trauma-informed practices would prevent the re-traumatisation of people in prison.

What follows are this dissertation's research objectives:

- To investigate the impact trauma can have on individuals, and how trauma exposure can manifest in behaviour of prisoners.

- To explore whether implementing trauma-informed practices in prisons could alleviate some of the deprivation felt by prisoners, by identifying potential benefits and barriers to success.

1.3 Methodology

This research uses a critical literature review, a method of synthesizing and collecting existing literature and research (Snyder, 2019). A critical literature review was chosen for this research because it tells a story that creates strong foundations to build upon the current understanding of a topic (Jesson and Lacey, 2006; Snyder, 2019). Effective critical literature reviews use a synthesis of literature using critical analysis to find the strengths, weaknesses, omissions, and bias of current literature, which shows how the research fits into the wider context of the topic (Jesson and Lacey, 2006). Another consideration when choosing the appropriate methodology was vulnerability; this research involves individuals who have been exposed to trauma, making them vulnerable people. Using primary research with vulnerable people as part of an undergraduate degree would not be accepted by The University Research Ethics Committee, therefore a critical literature review was chosen.

Thematic analysis was also used within this research. This is a form of qualitative analysis that provides a systematic element to data analysis (Alhojailan, 2012). It allows the researcher to identify the relationship between different concepts by identifying, analysing, and interpreting key patterns of meaning or themes within the literature. Importantly, thematic analysis does not simply summarize the existing literature (Clarke and Braun, 2016).

This research will access a wide array of literature using a variety of search engines including: The Leeds Beckett Library, Google Scholar, ResearchGate, and Elsevier, however, the author acknowledges there will be existing literature that meets the criteria of the research outside of these search engines that the author cannot identify (King, 2015).

1.4 Ethics

Ethical research must maintain the principles of justice, fairness, and respect through each process of the research (Sobočan et al., 2019). When research concerns itself with vulnerable individuals, it raises a range of ethical concerns such as: confidentiality, disclosure, risk of harm, and informed consent (Seedat et al., 2004). However critical literature reviews do not collect personal or sensitive information directly from participants, instead from sources which have already been subject to ethical approval (Suri, 2020). This ensures this dissertation will do no harm or illegal practices when gathering and interpreting research.

1.5 Dissertation structure

Chapter one will highlight how destructive trauma can be (Center for Substance Abuse Treatment (US), 2014b), harming the brain's foundation, affecting a child's ability to regulate their emotions to stress (Dunn et al., 2017), and worsening mental and physical health (Wittbrodt et al., 2020). It will aid understanding how prevalent trauma exposure is inside prison compared to the general population (Altintas and Bilici, 2018; Ford et al., 2020; Witt et al., 2019). The second chapter will discuss how in such a depriving environment trauma can manifest in behaviours such as: mental health issues, drug use, self-harm, self-inflicted deaths, and inmate-on-inmate assault (Haney, 2012). This chapter will discuss such behaviour as the result of trauma that has been exacerbated by an environment that is so harmful and depriving it re-traumatizes prisoners (Haney, 2012), using Syke's POI, the deprivation, importation, and combined models to explore this concept (Armour, 2012; Cao et al., 1997; DeLisi et al., 2004; Dye, 2010). The final chapter will explore whether becoming trauma-informed (BTI) could prevent people in prison being re-traumatized by reducing the deprivations posed upon them. This research acknowledges TIPs have developed a negative narrative within the literature (Kelman et al., 2024b). Nonetheless, this chapter will use findings from MCI Framingham to show that trauma-informed (TI) prisons can work and perform well when the environment allows them to (Levenson and Willis, 2018).

The following chapter will provide context for this research, discussing what trauma is, its impact, and the prevalence in prison.

Chapter 2: Trauma Key Theory

2.1 Introduction

This chapter will discuss what trauma is, using definitions from SAMHSA (2014a) and Blehm (2024), who critiques the former. It will then discuss how trauma can affect everyone differently, and that throughout childhood, adolescence, and adulthood, individuals are at heightened risk of experiencing different traumas (Center for Substance Abuse Treatment (US), 2014b; Koenen et al., 2011). This chapter will then discuss trauma theory, beginning with Ferenczi's early work, which paved the way for what is known today about trauma (Haynal, 2014; Kupermann, 2022). Contemporary trauma theory is also discussed, highlighting how individuals with experiences of trauma are extremely vulnerable (Constantian, 2019; Covington, 2001; Covington, 2022; Norman et al., 2012; Dye, 2018). This will lead onto the extent of trauma saturation in prison, using research from Altintas and Bilici (2018) and Ford et al. (2020) to highlight this. Finally, this chapter will discuss what Farmer's (2019) review, and The Female Offender Strategy suggest should be implemented to support these vulnerable individuals and their experience of the criminal justice system (CJS) (Ministry of Justice, 2018).

2.2 What is trauma?

Originating from the Greek word 'wound' (Kolaitis and Olf, 2017), the term trauma does not have an unanimously recognised definition within academic literature (Blehm, 2024). SAMHSA (2014a, p.7) define trauma as the result of "an event, series of events, or set of circumstances experienced by an individual as physically or emotionally harmful or life-threatening and that has lasting adverse effects on the individual's functioning and mental, physical, social, emotional, or spiritual well-being". SAMHSA's definition focuses on the effects of trauma, which is a common approach (Blehm, 2024). However, Blehm (2024) emphasises the significance of differentiating trauma from its effects, suggesting the undesirable emotional reaction to an event that is distinguished as petrifying, can disturb the way the individual identifies themselves with the event experienced. Creating a standardized definition of trauma is fundamentally challenging, it attempts to incorporate conditions for a subjective experience with criteria for an objective event (Krupnik, 2018).

2.3 Trauma at different life stages

Trauma presents itself differently in everybody, its impact can range from subtle to completely destructive. Some individuals noticeably display behaviour connected with post-traumatic stress

disorder (PTSD), whereas other individuals may display behaviour that is resilient or not recognised by diagnostic criteria (Center for Substance Abuse Treatment (US), 2014b).

Children under five are more likely to witness domestic violence than any other age, and in the middle of childhood there is a heightened risk of parental physical abuse than any other age (Koenen et al., 2011). Experiencing trauma as a young child can have detrimental consequences on the child's physiological, emotional, cognitive, and social function, including the capacity to relate to others and form empathy (Heide and Solomon, 2006). Adolescents are particularly vulnerable to bullying, embarrassment at school, and experimentation with drugs. Adolescents go through significant brain development, and physical and emotional growth (Eckes and Radunovich, 2007), therefore experiences of trauma in this stage of life can severely affect brain development and nervous system responsivity (Shaw, 2000).

Unfortunately, there is a large gap within the literature regarding trauma experienced in adulthood, with far less research available compared to trauma experienced in childhood. One could argue this is because adults are not seen as the 'real' ideal victim of trauma, whereas child victims are usually viewed as the 'real' ideal victim because they are young, innocent, blameless, and unable to freely consent (Spencer et al., 2020). DiBennardo (2018) suggests this narrative is enforced by the media; the stories involving child victims are prioritised over those of adult victims, additionally these media sources present victims who are adults as responsible for their victimisation. The limited literature available suggests adults have a heightened risk of experiencing intimate partner violence, which is associated with developing depression, anxiety, and suicide attempts (Pill et al., 2017). Further, experiences of psychological trauma in adulthood have a relationship with worsening health, mental health issues, chronic pain, and sleep disturbances (Wittbrodt et al., 2020).

Dunn et al. (2017) argue trauma experienced in childhood has the potential to be more detrimental than trauma experienced later in life. They dispute early trauma exposure compromises the child's ability to successfully complete stage-salient developmental tasks such as forming secure attachments. Further, they believe early trauma exposure harms the brain's foundations, therefore effecting the child's ability to regulate arousal, stress, and emotion (Dunn et al., 2017).

2.4 Trauma theory

The importance of trauma first emerged in Sandor Ferenczi's work (Haynal, 2014). His 1933 research was central to current understandings of trauma (Kupermann, 2022). Ferenczi believed trauma was a

central cause of neurotic and character pathology, even when other specialists disregarded this. Ferenczi focused on parental actions as trauma, suggesting when children experience trauma, they go into a state of paralysis, physically and mentally (Frankel, 1998). Ferenczi believed childhood trauma (CT) has long term consequences; children become detached from the world and use masturbation as an alternate for disappointed love (Frankel, 1998).

Contemporary theorists expanded on Ferenczi's work; Heide and Solomon (2006) found children exposed to trauma form insecure attachments to their guardians leading to developmental disruptions which can be consequential. When these children are in stressful situations, they struggle accessing areas of the brain key to logical thinking and appropriate decision making, instead exhibiting socially inappropriate behaviour. Van Beeck et al. (2024) also found experiences of CT leads to insecure attachments later in life to everyone not just guardians. Research also suggests CT increases the risk of developing chronic health issues, anxiety disorder, depressive disorder, attention deficit and hyperactive disorder (ADHD), problematic drug and alcohol use, victimisation in adulthood, suicidal behaviour, and interactions with the CJS (Constantian, 2019; Covington, 2001; Covington, 2022; Norman et al., 2012; Dye, 2018).

The literature suggests multiple experiences of CT can have severe consequences later in life. Briere et al. (2008) found the complexity of symptoms appears to increase when a cumulation of CTs are experienced. Repeated experiences of CT increase the chance of further exposure whether in childhood or later in life, because of the individual's inability to form relationships with others, increasing their vulnerability to further harm (Center for Substance Abuse Treatment (US), 2014a). The literature estimates experiencing sexual abuse in childhood doubles or triples the risk of sexual revictimisation later in life for women (Classen et al., 2005). This risk can have its own long-term effects on the individual, causing a wider array of symptoms in adulthood (Briere et al., 2008).

2.5 Trauma exposure in the prison population

Research by Altintas and Bilici (2018) highlights the prevalence of CT amongst 216 male and female prisoners from four prisons in Istanbul. Using the childhood trauma questionnaire (CTQ) they found 47% reported experiencing emotional abuse, 37% physical abuse, 49.5% sexual abuse, 68% emotional neglect, and 55.5% physical neglect. Similarly, findings from Ford et al.'s (2020) research in Wales, examining childhood adversities amongst 468 male prisoners found 84.2% reported experiencing at least one adverse childhood experience (ACE), and 45.5% reported being exposed to more than four ACEs. In comparison, Witt et al. (2019) surveyed 2,531 people (55.4% female and 44.6% male) from the

general population in Germany. They found 56.3% reported experiencing no childhood adversities, and only 8.9% reported experiencing more than four ACEs. In contrast 45.5% of Ford et al.'s (2020) sample of prisoners reported experiencing more than four ACEs, highlighting how trauma exposure is significantly embedded in prison life compared to the general population.

Given the impact of trauma on some people, as highlighted in this chapter, Farmer's (2019) review emphasizes how important it is that the CJS is TI from start to finish. This concept will be discussed in section 4.0. Similarly, the Female Offender Strategy suggests women should be kept out of prison where possible, so they avoid the chance of being re-traumatized in the painful prison environment. The programme is driven by three priorities: earlier intervention, importance on community-based solutions, and aiming to make custody as effective and reasonable as it can be for the women who must reside there (Ministry of Justice, 2018).

2.6 Summary

This chapter has discussed what trauma is, how different age groups are more at risk of experiencing different types of traumas (Koenen et al., 2011). Experiencing trauma at a young age can lead to those individuals forming poor attachments with people which disrupts their development (Heide and Solomon, 2006). Additionally, experiences of CT are associated with developing chronic health issues, anxiety disorder, depressive disorder, ADHD, problematic drug and alcohol use, victimisation in adulthood, suicidal behaviour, and interactions with the CJS (Constantian, 2019; Covington, 2001; Covington, 2022; Norman et al., 2012; Dye, 2018). Therefore, it comes as no surprise, prison is saturated with individuals who have been exposed to trauma, compared to the general population (Altintas and Bilici, 2018; Ford et al., 2020; Witt et al., 2019). Farmer's (2019) review and the Ministry of Justice's (2018) Female Offender Strategy place emphasis on the need for change to ensure people enter a system that is TI, and where possible prisons should be the last resort, to protect these vulnerable people rather than re-traumatise them.

The following chapter will build on the findings in this chapter to explore how trauma can manifest in violent and harmful behaviours.

Chapter 3: Deprivation, Violence and The Role of Prison Staff

3.1 Introduction

This chapter will explore violence within prison and its relation to trauma. As already established (refer to section 2.3 and 2.5), experiences of trauma can impact a person's physiological, emotional, cognitive, and social function (Heide and Solomon, 2006) and the prison environment is saturated with trauma (Altintas and Bilici, 2018; Ford et al., 2020). This will provide context throughout this chapter, as prison violence will be discussed as the result of trauma exacerbated by the prison environment. This chapter will introduce three themes: deprivation, violence, and prison staff. The first introduces Sykes's POI (Armour, 2012) to provide the reader with basic context of what this theory suggests, which will be applied throughout the first and second theme. Next, the gendered POI will be discussed, which will highlight how different prison-based populations can experience deprivations of prison differently and how this affects them (Ugelvik 2014; Mignon and Ransford, 2012; Breuer et al., 2021). This chapter will then examine different 'maladaptive' behaviours and discuss what the existing literature suggests can cause such behaviours. Discussing whether these behaviours are the result of a depriving environment, individual characteristics imported from outside prison, or a combination of both (Shammas, 2017; Dye, 2010). Finally, this chapter will discuss how the prison environment can affect prison staff, revealing the alarming amount of prison staff that have witnessed or experienced a traumatic event at work (Bell et al., 2019) and how prisons' failure to support those who have been victimised can be detrimental to staff's personal life (Barry, 2017; Keena et al., 2022; Duggins, 2023).

3.2 Deprivation

3.2.1 Introducing the pains of imprisonment

The literature shows that many prisoners have a history of trauma (Armour, 2012), but prisons themselves are traumatising, and can become a place of re-traumatisation for many (CroleRees et al., 2024; Haney, 2012). Prison is an environment with extreme levels of deprivation, degradation, and danger, that has the potential to cause harm to those living within it, which can have detrimental consequences on the inmates' physical and mental health (Haney, 2012). The deprivation model explains how the stressful and oppressive prison environment can cause maladaptation (Cao et al., 1997), and deprivation theorists suggest this maladaptation is attributable to Sykes's POI (Armour,

2012). POI attempts to explain why prison life is challenging through five significant deprivations: liberty, goods and services, heterosexual relationships, autonomy, and security (Shammas, 2017). Experiencing these deprivations is argued to cause increased tension, anxiety, violence, and reoffending (Shammas, 2017). Conversely, importation theorists argue, inmates' maladaptation is attributable to attitudes, values, beliefs, and behaviours they import into prison from their outside life (DeLisi et al., 2004). From a trauma perspective, the combined model best explains behaviour and trauma within prison, recognising that prisoners can have extensive histories of trauma, and coming into the prison environment increases the likelihood of experiencing more traumatic events because of how painful prison life is (Dye, 2010). Overall, research suggests that prison life can be detrimental and traumatising to many living inside.

3.2.2 Gendered pains of imprisonment

Sykes' POI can be expanded to be inclusive to all prison-based populations, regardless of gender (Haggerty and Bucierus, 2020). Ugelvik (2014) argues prison can be seen to challenge masculinity. Certain values, practices, and characteristics can be seen as typically male, and the values, practices, and characteristics of a man who enters prison counteract these. It could be argued a 'real man' would not find himself making decisions that result in him entering prison, a 'real man' would make 'the right' decisions, he is trustworthy, someone to rely on, and is someone with morals and agency (Ugelvik 2014). The infantilising prison routine gives prisoners little opportunity to structure their day (Haggerty and Bucierus, 2020), stripping them of all decisions from when to wake up, when or what to eat, and what to wear (Ugelvik 2014). These decisions would be typical of any adult; therefore, this loss of autonomy, as described in the POI (Armour, 2012) can challenge the imprisoned males' view of their masculinity (Ugelvik 2014).

It has been reported women have a more painful experience in prison than their male counterparts, yet women remain under-researched in this field (Crewe et al., 2017). Baldwin (2018) states prison life is difficult and emotional for most women, but particularly challenging for incarcerated mothers, disrupting and destroying motherhood. Prison separates mothers from children, reduces or removes their maternal role, and creates painful experiences of pregnancy and childbirth in prison (Mitchell, 2024). The House of Commons Justice Committee (2022) found many incarcerated mothers had no physical contact with their children in over a year. This physical separation between mothers and their children makes maintaining contact extremely complicated (Breuer et al., 2021). Research suggests limited contact with children has been a contributor to heightened stress among incarcerated mothers, the loss of strong family ties exacerbating previous trauma (Mignon and Ransford, 2012; Breuer et al.,

2021). However, for women the gendered POI are not limited to motherhood, women in prison are vulnerable to day-to-day humiliation relating to sanitary products, strip searches as sexual coercion, and sexual assault by prison staff (Haggerty and Bucierius, 2020). These findings highlight the importance of acknowledging the gendered POI, because the deprivations of prison can be experienced differently in different prison-based populations.

3.2.3 Mental health

Mental health is a serious problem in prisons, adversely affect existing mental health issues and produce new issues. Semenza and Grosholz (2019) suggest there are 10 times more people with mental health problems in prison than in mental hospitals. This high estimate is reflected in the House of Commons' (2021) report that found 47% of men and 71% of women in prison self-reported mental health issues in 2019-20. Augsburg et al. (2022) contends imprisonment exacerbates prisoners' mental health, finding 68.3% of incarcerated women felt their mental health had deteriorated during imprisonment. Similar findings from Al-Rousan et al. (2017) show how many months it took for a diagnosis of depression (26.2), anxiety (24.4), personality disorder (29.5), and PTSD (21), suggesting the prisoners' mental health was worsened to the point of diagnoses during imprisonment or imprisonment caused mental health problems. Haney (2017) argues prisoners who experience problems with mental health suffer because they are treated by understaffed, overworked, and inexperienced staff. The deprivation model argues depriving environments, where overcrowding is high, family contact is low, and duration of solitary confinement explain the significant amount of mental health issues in prison (Edgemon and Clay-Warner, 2018). This is evident in Goomany and Dickinson's (2015) findings; mental health was severely affected by the lack of activities and mental stimulation experienced during long periods of time spent in isolation, some prisoners reporting spending up to 23 hours a day locked up (Nurse et al., 2003). Although, there is some research to suggest mental health improves in women during imprisonment (Harner and Riley, 2013), the prevalence of mental health issues among prisoners is dangerously high and findings show how the prison and its staff can worsen these effects.

3.2.4 Drug use

The prison environment is a place where drug use is high. The level of drug use in prisons is of significant concern. However, there is uncertainty around the data available regarding drug use in prisons because of its illegality (Kolind and Duke, 2016). Acknowledging this, research estimates 75,000 drug users go through the prison system in England and Wales each year (O'Hagan and Hardwick, 2017), Gillespie (2005) found the literature varies from 22% to 60% of prisoners use drugs, varying between prisons. In many countries, the most common drug used in prison is cannabis (Norman, 2022). Using Sykes' POI, it

could be argued prisoners use drugs because they are deprived of security; feeling safe inside prison is naturally hard to induce because prisons are innately violent (Shammas, 2017). Cope (2003) suggests many prisoners used cannabis to aid sleep, to pass time, to calm down, or to slip away from reality. Other scholars suggest drug use in prison is a maladaptive coping mechanism for the deprivation, depression, and negative emotions they face from the environment inside (Pelissier and Jones, N., 2006; Leban et al., 2015; Listwan et al., 2013). Nevertheless, there are devastating consequences to drug use. The Office for National Statistics (2023) established between 2008 and 2019 there were 145 drug-related deaths in prisons in England and Wales, after 2015 the rate of male prisoners dying from drug poisoning was higher than men in the general population, highlighting the issue drug use poses on prisoners. These findings indicate the use of drugs among prisoners is exacerbated by the deprivations they face day to day, and when not addressed the consequences are damaging.

3.3 Violence

3.3.1 Self-harm

Self-harm is a common occurrence among prisoners (Ryland et al., 2020). Rates in both men and women are significantly higher than the general population (Hawton et al., 2014). Favril et al. (2020) states prison self-harm rates amongst men are estimated around 5% to 6% and in women 20% to 24%, compared to less than 1% in the general population. In the 12 months to September 2024, prisons in England and Wales recorded 891 self-harm incidents per 1,000 prisoners (77,869), an 11% increase on the previous year (Ministry of Justice, 2025). There is extensive research showing mental illness such as depression, bipolar disorder, anxiety disorder, and schizophrenia are strongly associated with a heightened risk of self-harm (Singhal et al., 2014; Gates et al., 2017). As mentioned in section 3.2.3, mental illness is a significant problem in prisons (Semenza and Grosholz, 2019). Therefore, mental illness is likely to be a significant factor in predicting self-harm, nevertheless different academics believe prisoners self-harm for different reasons. Brezean et al. (2016) argues self-harm rates are so high because of how stressful the prison environment is, they state prisoners believe self-harm can be advantageous, as it results in hospitalisation and the associated improved living conditions. Whereas Sousa et al. (2019) stress this view can be damaging and cause more harmful behaviour. Using the deprivation model, one could argue overcrowding does cause self-harm as prisoners have to endure further deprivation; for example, an overcrowded prison may have more prisoners sharing cells, therefore these prisoners are deprived of their privacy, which is argued to cause 'maladaptive' behaviour such as self-harm (Shammas, 2017). Baggio et al. (2018) found a relationship between overcrowding and self-harm rates, when overcrowding increased, self-harm rates became more

prevalent. Conversely, Kenning et al. (2010) documented anger as a cause of self-harm in prison, many women described their experiences as impulsive acts associated with anger, hurt, or frustration. Self-harm in this sense is a form of self-punishment to relieve pain and frustration. There is an array of reasons why a prisoner may self-harm, from mental illnesses to overcrowding problems, but it is clear the literature suggests it is a significant problem and is complex to solve.

3.3.2 Self-inflicted deaths

Although there is very little interest from the public in prison violence (Towl et al., 2017), Bukten and Stavseth (2021) argue self-inflicted deaths are the most common cause of death in prisons. The rate of self-inflicted deaths among the prison population is dramatically higher than in the general population (Zhong et al., 2021), in England and Wales it is five times higher (Fazel et al., 2008). In the 12 months up to December 2024, 89 individuals in prisons in England and Wales took their own life (Ministry of Justice, 2025). Frühwald and Frottier (2005) found evidence to suggest mental illness strongly predicted suicide, particularly as there is little support provided for those struggling with their mental health. However, there is evidence to suggest mental illnesses are not the sole cause of suicide, Goyes (2024) argues pre-prison trauma has a part to play in suicide because it makes prisoners more vulnerable to negative emotions and decreases their tolerance to stress. Clements-Nolle et al. (2009) support this claim finding female prisoners with histories of suicide attempts were more likely to report experiencing trauma in their childhood. Bukten and Stavseth's (2021) contributions suggest the prison environment increases the likelihood of suicide, they state the lack of visits from family and friends and feelings of isolation are associated with suicide. Similarly, Suto and Arnaut (2010) suggest prisoners experience feelings of depression when being transferred to different institutions or areas, and feelings of heightened stress experienced from employment within the prison. Suto and Arnaut (2010) further argue relationship issues can lead to suicide attempts. Prisoners explained the loss of ties with family and friends, physical gifts, threats and animosity with other inmates, and poor relationships with staff all contributed to suicidal feelings and behaviour. These findings highlight the painful and depriving prison environment can contribute to prison suicide, but some individuals will react differently to these pains depending on their level of vulnerability, such as previous mental health issues (Dye, 2010). This notion is supported by the combined model, which argues some individuals in prison are more vulnerable than others, and the painful prison environment can exacerbate these vulnerabilities leading to suicide attempts (Edgemon, 2016). Suicide is complex and cannot be explained by one factor alone, a myriad of circumstances such as mental illness, pre-prison trauma, prison factors, and relationship issues are all contributory.

3.3.3 Inmate-on-inmate assault

Violence is an everyday occurrence in prison life, unsurprising when groups of people with antisocial behaviour are confined into depriving institutions (Wolff et al., 2007). In the 12 months leading to September 2024 there were 29,881 inmate-on-inmate assaults in England and Wales (Ministry of Justice, 2025). However, it is important to highlight these figures are thought to be severely under-reported because of concerns of punishments among prisoners (Robinson and Forrester, 2023). While physical violence in prison is widely recognised, there is little research surrounding its prevalence or predictors (Wolff et al., 2009). Wooldredge (2020) found prison culture contributed to prison violence, however there was larger emphasis on the prison management, arguing the staff have the most impact on prisoners' perception of prison life. Much of the literature surrounding violence in prison focuses on sexual victimisation, the Prison Reform Trust (2021) reported 256 sexual assaults occurred in 2021. Wolff et al. (2006) states sexual assault in prisons is commonly in the form of unwanted sexual touching of breasts, genitals, or buttocks. Levan (2016) found numerous negative impacts of sexual and physical assault in prison, such as physical injury, sexually transmitted diseases, and PTSD. Additionally, Levan (2016) found high levels of anxiety, fear, and social disruption, a broken sense of manhood, and feelings of incompetence and insecurity were caused by sexual and physical assault in prison. Struckman-Johnson and Struckman-Johnson (2000) found factors such as large population, racial conflict, barracks housing, and inadequate security increased the rates of sexual assault, suggesting inmate-on-inmate assaults are a result of factors from within the prison, rather than prisoners' characteristics. This contrasts with the importation model, that prisoners' demographic, social, and psychological factors are not the cause of inmate-on-inmate violence, instead environmental factors are suggested to have more of an influence to predict this type of violence (Dye, 2010).

3.4 Prison staff

3.4.1 Trauma exposure

Working in prisons heightens the risk of exposure to violence compared to other jobs (Steiner and Wooldredge, 2016). Prison staff work in environments saturated with trauma (Bell et al., 2019), and not only work with individuals who have experiences of trauma, which in itself is emotionally demanding (Kenning et al., 2010) but spend considerable amounts of time exposed to the deprivations of prisons (Bierie, 2010). When exploring experiences of traumatic events in prison Bell et al. (2019) found all staff in their sample had experienced or witnessed an event that was traumatising, 53% had thoughts of suicide and self-harm expressed to them over 50 times, and 60% had witnessed self-harm or attempted suicide over 30 times. This distressing exposure can develop into secondary traumatisation, which

manifests through anxiety, depression, intrusive thoughts, and PTSD-like symptoms (Johnson, 2017; Elwood et al., 2011). Crawley (2013) states prison staff can become very distressed after a suicide of a prisoner, especially for officers who find the body. This is evident in research conducted by Barry (2017), finding 13 of the 14 prison officers had experienced a death by suicide. One officer described feeling hesitant about attending night shifts following a death.

Further, Barry (2017) noted one officer who experienced a suicide by hanging, had faced enduring effects not only at work, but also in his personal life; he became extremely cautious about anything around necks, particularly with his children. From this research it is well established that exposure to trauma is an occupational hazard for those working in prison (Bell et al., 2019). As prison staff are instrumental to the success of prisons (Lambert et al., 2009) it is important to highlight not only the detrimental effects prison poses on prisoners but also the individuals working there.

3.4.2 Inmate-on-officer assault

The fear of becoming victimised at work can increase psychological strain on staff, and working in a prison increases the chances of getting injured (Keena et al., 2022). McNeeley (2021) states prisoner-on-staff assaults are one of the largest threats to employee safety in prison, this is evident in England and Wales, where 10,496 assaults against staff were recorded in the 12 months to September 2024 (Ministry of Justice, 2025). In fact, Sorensen et al. (2011) argues although events such as arson, escapes, homicides, and riots have significantly decreased since the 1980s, assaults against prison staff have stayed consistently high. Wortley (2002) states the dynamic of assaults against staff differ from assaults against other inmates because of the nature of their relationship; prisoners and staff have an adverse relationship from the beginning, due to staff exercising authority over inmates (Stoliker, 2016). When examining inmate-on-staff assaults, Sorensen et al. (2011) found male officers were more likely to be assaulted than female officers, 48.2% of assaults were against White officers, which is reflective of the officer population, however, Hispanics were over-represented and Black officers were under-represented as victims. They found the most common form of assault was beating with fists, being kicked or bitten (54.4%) followed by stabbing with knives or shanks (26.6%), with most assaults resulting in minor or moderate injuries needing only outpatient care (Sorensen et al., 2011). Even when an assault results in minor injuries, it has been found officers do not receive adequate support (Duggins, 2023). Participants in research by Duggins (2023, p.69) described their assault to “trigger something”, a participant described how they did not receive enough time off work after the assault, even though the event was described as traumatic. This research shows the intensity of the rate of assaults against

prison staff, and even when not considered serious, the assault can have damaging effects on staff wellbeing.

3.5 Summary

This chapter discussed violence in prisons and how it causes trauma for those living and working inside. The first theme found prisons are full of deprivation; depriving mothers from seeing their children (Mitchell, 2024), exacerbating mental health issues (Augsburger et al., 2022), and drugs used as a coping mechanism to deal with the deprivations (Pelissier and Jones, N., 2006). The second theme discussed violence, finding self-harm a complex problem to solve with many academics suggesting different reasons for its cause from mental illness (Singhal et al., 2014) to anger (Kenning et al., 2010). Similarly, highlighting the complexity of suicide, factors such as mental illness (Frühwald and Frottier, 2005) pre-prison trauma (Goyes, 2024), prison factors (Bukten and Stavseth, 2021), and relationship issues (Suto and Arnaut, 2010) can contribute to suicide. Inmate-on-inmate assault were shown to be a severe problem which can result in physical injury, sexually transmitted diseases, and PTSD (Levan, 2016). The final theme discussed prison staff, finding trauma exposure was part of all prison staff's daily life (Bell et al., 2019); and assault against staff is a consistent problem (Sorensen et al. 2011) traumatising staff when they do not get the required support (Duggins, 2023).

The following chapter will discuss TIPs, and whether they can alleviate some of the deprivations, in turn preventing re-traumatisation.

Chapter 4: Trauma-Informed Practices in Prison

4.1 Introduction

This chapter will explore what it means to become TI and whether this could prevent the re-traumatisation of people in prison. Firstly, this chapter will discuss what becoming TI entails for prisons; highlighting how men and women with experiences of trauma may react ‘noncompliantly’ to procedures like pat-downs or be unwilling to admit certain past traumatic experiences at all due to perceived weakness (Covington, 2022; Cesaroni et al., 2023). This chapter will then examine the five principles that TIP’s ‘do no harm approach’ was created and sustained upon (Miller and Najavits, 2012; Vaswani and Paul, 2019). Exploring safety, trustworthiness, choice, collaboration, and empowerment this chapter will discuss how enhancing these feelings can be beneficial for both the prisoners and staff in relation to the previous chapter’s findings, of drug use, self-harm, self-inflicted deaths, assaults, and trauma exposure. Finally, this chapter will discuss whether implementing TIPs in prisons can prevent these behaviours and re-traumatisation in prison, debating factors such as funding, leadership, and overcrowding.

4.2 Becoming trauma-informed

BTI involves acknowledging the potentially long-term effects that trauma exposure has on individuals, even if the individual does not recognise they have experienced a traumatic event, in this acknowledgement, the prison provides appropriate care to those individuals (McCartan, 2020; Kubiak et al., 2017). However, it must be noted, there is no unanimously agreed definition of what trauma-informed care (TIC) entails (Kelman et al., 2024a). As highlighted in section 2.5, many individuals who interact with the CJS have past experiences of trauma (Altintas and Bilici, 2018; Ford et al., 2020), the harsh conditions of the prison environment have the potential to re-traumatise these individuals, see section 3.2.1 (Haney, 2012). BTI is supported by both the Female Offender Strategy and the Farmer review, whom both aim to make custody as effective and decent as it can be for the women who do have to enter the CJS while also preventing reoffending and strengthening family relationships (Farmer, 2019; Ministry of Justice, 2018).

All staff members get specially trained, so they understand trauma and its connection to mental health, substance use, behaviour challenges, physical health issues, and changes to brain development

(Covington, 2022). This training triggers a change of perspective, instead of asking individuals “What’s wrong with you?” it shifts to “What happened to you?” (McCartan, 2020, p.8). This ‘do no harm’ approach trains staff to be conscious of the impacts of trauma and aims as a minimum to provide an environment where individuals are not retraumatized, nor does their trauma become an impediment to engaging with support services (Miller and Najavits, 2012; Vaswani and Paul, 2019). Such an environment is created and sustained under five key principles: safety, trustworthiness, choice, collaboration, and empowerment (Vaswani and Paul, 2019). These five principles contradict trauma, they aim to give the individuals power and control over their traumatic experiences (Reilly, 2024) and will be discussed later in this chapter (refer to section 4.3).

Trauma manifests significantly differently in men and women, and practising TIC recognises this. For example, men may struggle to accept their experience as traumatic because of their sense of masculinity, not wanting to be perceived as weak, hindering help-seeking behaviours in prison (Cesaroni et al., 2023). Women may fear being touched by prison officers, particularly male officers, causing the women to be seen as noncompliant with procedures such as pat downs, when in reality their behaviour can be a response to previous victimisation (Covington, 2022). Although much of the literature surrounding TIC in prisons is focused on women, there is evidence to suggest TIC can result in improved outcomes for all individuals involved. For example, a TI workforce increases staff job satisfaction, reduces staff turnover, improves relationships between staff and prisoners, increases appropriate responses to both prisoner and staff needs, decreases the need for restraining techniques, and reduces recidivism rates (Bradley, 2021).

The positive outcomes of TIC led women’s prisons across England and Wales to aim to become TI in 2015 (Kelman et al., 2024a). This initiative was based on the work of Dr Stephanie Covington, and financially supported by the charitable organisation, One Small Thing (Auty et al., 2022). BTI training was implemented in all 12 women’s prisons between 2015-2017 and training began in the long-term high-secure male estate in 2018 (Auty et al., 2022), with estimates of around 4,000 staff members and selected prisoners. The BTI training aims to instil TIP in all levels of the prison with frequent discussions with Governors, Prison Officer BTI Leads, Guide Teams, and prisoner peer monitors (Auty et al., 2022). The BTI training was wellreceived by staff, who reported it to be relevant, informative, and useful (Auty et al., 2022). Additionally, TI interventions such as Seeking Safety, Helping Women Recover/Beyond Trauma, Beyond Violence, and Esuba have been developed for imprisoned women. These interventions promote awareness surrounding the significant impacts of trauma and aid recovery for the individual, whether they experienced trauma as a singular event or multiple events over time (King, 2015).

4.3 Trauma-informed principles

4.3.1 Safety

As found in sections 3.3.3 and 3.4.2, safety in prison is inherently compromised; there were 29,881 inmate-on-inmate assaults and 10,496 inmate-on-officer assaults in England and Wales in the 12 months to September 2024 (Ministry of Justice, 2025). Processes such as strip searches, staff use of authority, and challenging relationships can create feelings of unsafeness and potentially trigger memories of traumatic experiences (Auty et al., 2022). Instead, TI environments aim to prevent the chance of re-traumatisation and enhance safety by: implementing policies for same-sex strip searches, pat-downs, and exams; ensure staff do not engage in physical touching without informing the individual first; if there is a current policy in place for strip searches for inmates after contact visits, offer the chance to have a noncontact visit instead; use a manner of respect directed towards all individuals, for example prison staff should call prisoners by their name instead of their identification number (Miller and Najavits, 2012). Treisman (2021) argues language, in the context of trauma, can play a significant role in enhancing feelings of safety and preventing re-traumatisation. The connection of trauma experiences and the role of language is multilayered and complex, language can contribute to trauma (Busch and McNamara, 2020). For example, children and adults who have experienced abuse in their past may have been the victim of negative words and threatening language, such as “I wish you weren’t born” or “It’s all your fault” (Treisman, 2021, p.12). This language holds weight and is very powerful in terms of shaping an individual’s lens, attitudes, feelings, beliefs, and perspectives towards others and themselves (Treisman, 2021). The use of problematic language often results in re-traumatisation, so training staff members within prison with TI language skills equips them with the abilities needed to end the cycle of re-traumatisation, which benefits both prisoners and staff (Hart et al., 2024).

When TIP is effectively implemented in prison, safety significantly improves, MCI Framingham saw inmate-on-inmate assaults decrease by 54%, inmate-on-staff assaults decrease by 62%, suicide attempts decrease by 60%, and self-injury incidents decrease by 13% (Benedict and CORE Associates, 2014). These changes would be beneficial for everybody, arguably prisoners and staff feel safer inside prison because assaults on prisoners and staff decreased, and they are exposed to fewer events of self-injury and suicide attempts. However, it must be recognised that TIP cannot thrive in a trauma-inducing environment, as established in section 3.0 prisons are inherently unsafe. This is difficult to overcome without radical changes to prison organisational culture and policy (Malik et al., 2021).

4.3.2 Trustworthiness

Those who have been exposed to trauma are more likely to be distrusting of others (Waite, 2024), therefore, it is not surprising that prisons are often described as low trust environments that house individuals who have often had their trust eroded or destroyed (Waite, 2023a). Historically, staff-prisoner relationships have been difficult, prisoners often have experiences where their trust has been broken by the CJS, raising the question why should these individuals trust those in the system that has harmed them? (Waite, 2024). However, trust plays a significant role in staff-prisoner relationships (Waite, 2023b). Nevertheless, this trust can be compromised as prison staff members often believe their behaviour needs to be forceful to convey authority and power, often expressed through yelling or name calling. However, prisoners understand the officers' level of authority and the power imbalance without the need for these forceful behaviours, instead they want to be treated calmly with dignity and respect (Miller and Najavits, 2012). In relation to individuals with trauma, a conundrum is faced for staff-prisoner relationships, as building trust requires trauma to be overcome, and trust must be restored to overcome trauma (Waite, 2023a).

Relational-Cultural Theory suggests relationships are not just a means to an end, instead good strong relationships promote healthy development (Zhang, 2022). Such healthy development is evident in findings from Bradley (2017), who found positive staff-prisoner relationships gave prisoners someone to talk to and gave them the opportunity to get counselling, which can increase the level of trust between prisoners and staff. Liebling et al. (2011) found strong staff-prisoner relationships were significant for many reasons: helping officers gain intelligence to make the prison run smoothly; prisoners need strong relationships as staff help them attain things they want or need; and strong relationships between staff and prisoners are humane, making prison work or life easier. However, negative staff-prisoner relationships can promote mistrust, a feeling that is particularly prevalent in prisons (Farmer, 2019). One behaviour that has the potential to promote mistrust includes negative attitudes to self-harm; Bradley (2017) found officers often believe prisoners have learnt to self-harm to get what they want. This attitude and belief can have detrimental effects, as previously established in section 3.3.1, self-harm in prison is a significant problem (Ministry of Justice, 2025). These attitudes can result in lower levels of trust, consequently leading to under-reporting of trauma, as prisoners do not feel comfortable opening up with staff about their emotions or past traumatic experiences (Bradley, 2017; Kelman et al., 2024a).

4.3.3 Choice

Prison life is often characterised by the lack of choice and autonomy (Kaa-Deeder et al., 2017). Prisoners have limited freedom to choose what or when to engage in activities (Driessen et al., 2023); they have little choice when to wake up, eat, work, sleep, and what to wear, as all are determined by the institution's rules and schedule (Goodstein et al., 1984). Additionally, those who have experienced trauma, such as intimate-partner violence, enter prison with already diminished autonomy (Ciurria, 2018). Therefore, TIP aims not to exacerbate this loss but instead maximise their sense of choice and autonomy by asking the prisoners how they would like to be addressed, giving them a choice of the type of services they would prefer to match their present concerns (SAMHSA, 2014b). As referred to in section 3.2.1 the infantilising, arguably dehumanising consequences loss of autonomy produces is emphasised in Sykes' POI (Shammas, 2017). Statham et al. (2020) further suggests the longer the prisoner's sentence, the more ingrained the loss of autonomy becomes in their life, where long-term prisoners enter a child-like state now unable to make decisions for themselves. Personal autonomy is essential for prisoners, Driessen et al. (2023) suggest it has a direct positive influence on behaviour and how prisoners view prison life. Supporting evidence from Kaa-Deeder et al. (2017) suggests if prisoners perceive they have a choice in decisions it is positively related to better quality of life. However, Steiner (1979) and Lacey (1979) (cited in, Goodstein et al., 1984) suggest on the occasion when prisoners are given the opportunity to choose, they are still not exercising much control of the situation as the 'choice' is often from several options which are equally unfavourable, for example: whether to eat or not eat potatoes with their meal (Goodstein et al., 1984). Goodstein et al. (1984) further state when prisoners cannot exercise freedom of choice, they must take control of their life in other ways, like through drug use, and as highlighted in section 3.2.4, the level of drug use is of significant concern with 145 drug-related deaths between 2008 and 2019 (The Office for National Statistics, 2023) therefore the lack of choice can only worsen this issue. Importantly, TIP not only seeks to help reinforce prisoner autonomy and choice but also staff's (SAMHSA, 2014b). Section 3.4.1 found exposure to trauma is an occupational hazard for prison staff (Bell et al., 2019), therefore TI prisons aim to provide staff with resources and choices to support them when processing emotionally charged events (SAMHSA, 2014b). These resources have the potential to alleviate prison staff stress.

4.3.4 Collaboration

There is a natural overlap between choice and collaboration, prison staff cannot collaborate successfully with prisoners without giving them some level of choice. As established in section 4.3.3, prisoners experience little choice with many of their daily activities, having detrimental consequences (Goodstein et al., 1984). A TI environment recognises everyone within the organisation has a part to

play in the success of such an approach, meaning prisoners must be given the choice to collaborate in different activities (SAMHSA, 2014a). Uglean (2024) states being TI is different from other practices as it gives its users the opportunity to engage more with their care and create therapeutic relationships with staff. Prisoners can take charge of their lives as they are given the chance to collaborate with staff on their treatment, for example, they are asked if they would like the door open or closed or would like to be asked more questions or to speak freely or ask for advice on how to improve future treatment programmes (Uglean, 2024). Prisoners need a voice in the planning of their treatment and to have an active role in decisions. Implementing this principle represents a significant shift for prisons, as importance is placed on levelling the power difference between staff and prisoners

(Wright and Laurent, 2021; SAMHSA, 2014a). In traditional care, staff direct the course without much opportunity for patient feedback, but TIC encourages prisoners to have a voice (Menschner and Maul, 2016). Although TIC was established to treat individuals with histories of trauma, it also benefits staff as it helps reduce staff burnout (Uglean, 2024), as found in section 3.4.1, working in prison can be very distressing for many as they are exposed to the effects of trauma everyday (Bell et al., 2019). However, high rates of staff turnover and low staffing make it difficult for prisoners to build healing relationships with staff (Crole-Rees et al., 2023). The Prison Reform Trust (2022) found 50% of prison officers who left the previous year had been in the role for less than three years, and 26% left the service after less than a year. It is essential that staff turnover is reduced in order to fulfil the promises of TIC, as staff-prisoner relationships, healing, and trust risk being compromised (Hardan et al., 2023).

4.3.5 Empowerment

The nature of prison and its clear power structures make embodying the principal empowerment seem difficult (McMinn et al., 2023). There are visible and invisible elements that enforce these power structures, for example: visible includes the physical prison building, the uniformed guards who carry the keys to freedom; and invisible includes prisoners not entering prison willingly (McMinn et al., 2023). Despite this, TIP offers opportunities to empower its users, for example, staff can provide trauma-specific therapies and interventions designed to promote trauma recovery (Miller and Najavits, 2012). These options within the prison system are currently limited, but providing support is essential to avoid creating an environment that re-traumatises people (Reilly, 2024). These TI interventions and therapies place emphasis on empowerment, allowing users to connect with and support others, giving them a sense of belonging where they are unconditionally accepted (Covington and Bloom, 2007). This experience enhances feelings of empowerment and safety, another TIP principle (Petrillo, 2021; Vaswani and Paul, 2019). Such feelings are especially beneficial for prisoners struggling with addiction,

as highlighted by Covington and Bloom (2007) trauma and addiction are interrelated issues particularly for female offenders. This is evident in findings from this dissertation; O'Hagan and Hardwick (2017) estimated 75,000 drug users go through the prison system every year and findings from Altintas and Bilici (2018) and Ford et al. (2020) suggest many prisoners, female and male, have experiences of exposure to trauma (see section 3.2.4 and 2.5). According to the self-medication hypothesis of substance abuse, individuals use substances to manage the stress of their trauma or to numb their feelings (The National Child Traumatic Stress Network, 2008). Petrillo (2021) found taking part in Healing Trauma, a TI intervention, made women both individually and psychologically more empowered as they were taught to approach stress differently and consequently, they felt more in control of their responses (Messina and Calhoun, 2020), which may help women struggling with addiction to control their stress without turning to drugs or alcohol. Beyond Violence sessions, another TI intervention, were found to significantly reduce PTSD symptoms, and produced greater decreases in anxiety and anger measures than the control group (Messina and Calhoun, 2020).

4.4 Practical implications

This dissertation has established prisons were designed to house perpetrators not victims of trauma and is an environment inherently hard to implement TIPs (Miller and Najavits, 2012). Prisons attempting to implement TIPs require a change to their fundamental approach involving workforce upskilling, environmental change, organisational change, and development of clear referral pathways, but also significant funding and strong leadership. Without this, TIPs cannot be successfully implemented due to the lack of funds to train staff in BTI (Huo et al., 2023; Uglean, 2024). This training is essential, even experienced staff who have developed good capacities to react to trauma-responsive behaviour, typically still lack formal training and may be subject to burn out due to intense environmental working conditions (Miller and Najavits, 2012). Evidenced in section 3.4.1, one prison officer was enduring the harmful effects of working in and around a trauma-saturated environment not only at work but also in his personal life (Barry, 2017). However, other staff members may not be in the position where they can recognise or articulate how they are being adversely impacted at work, but implementing TIPs in prisons recognises that trauma can affect both staff and prisoners differently (Marris, 2023).

Lack of support from the leadership team can be a challenge for TIPs, because they are the actor that approves budgets, policies, and environmental changes within the prison. It is crucial to have a good relationship between the leadership team and employees as otherwise budgets could be restricted, and staff would not receive adequate BTI training (Uglean, 2024). Strong TIP leadership focuses on building a foundation of safety and trust between the managerial team and its employees, whereas

differing styles rely on controlling and manipulating their staff by threats to fire them (Uglean, 2024). Marris (2023) found when staff trusted their organisations, they reported 74% less stress, 106% more energy at work, 50% higher productivity, and 40% less burnout. However, high rates of staff turnover make it difficult to train staff in BTI if the initial training period has ended (Hardan et al., 2023), and as found in section 4.3.4, staff turnover is a significant issue in prisons in England and Wales (Prison Reform Trust, 2022). Staff turnover can therefore be a significant issue to the success of TIP, as it requires extensive training (Hardan et al., 2023).

High staff turnover is also a threat to trauma healing. It is well recognised that staff-prisoner relationships are at the “heart of the prison” (Crewe et al., 2022 p.925) and evidence shows feeling connected to others is linked to positive outcomes, especially in times of stress or trauma (Schultz et al., 2016). Joanne, a female prisoner in research by Waite (2023b, p.517) described how strong staff-prisoner relationships are essential for prisoners, as “to be able to trust staff, its everything...in here you don’t have anyone”. Building these strong relationships may prove difficult when staff are not staying for prolonged periods of time, therefore staff can exacerbate trauma rather than help to heal. These poor relationships can still exist in prisons that practice TIC, which could be due to lack of training or high staff turnover. The recent report by the Chief Inspector of Prisons (2025) found women’s prisons in England and Wales, although implementing TIPs, are still not doing enough to help women cope, even when it comes to their basic needs like clean underwear, causing so much distress for some prisoners it has led to women harming themselves. Kelman et al. (2024b) found most prisoners in their sample were unaware BTI training had even occurred as many staff still were “not very understanding” and staff were “not acting very differently” (p.327). These poor relationships are also exacerbated by issues of overcrowding. A prison is classified as crowded when it exceeds the number of prisoners of the institutions’ Certified Normal Accommodation (CNA) (Sturge, 2024). As of May 2024 60% of prisons in England and Wales are reported to be crowded, these prisons held just under 10,000 more prisoners than the CNA of these institutions (Sturge, 2024). If TIC is properly implemented, it has the potential to ameliorate the traumas experienced by prisoners and staff, but the practices are intrinsically linked to and rely on the environmental context in which they take place (Jewkes et al., 2019). TI prisons require a trusting, collaborative, safe, and empowering environment that abstains from retraumatising, essentially an environment which allows TIPs to flourish (Levenson and Willis, 2018). Unfortunately, issues such as funding, staff turnover, and overcrowding threaten the success of this approach as they limit the extent that BTI training can succeed and limit staff ability to form relationships with prisoners which hinders trauma healing.

4.5 Summary

This chapter explored what it means to become TI within prison, acknowledging the potential effects that trauma exposure can have on individuals, even when individuals are not aware they have experienced something potentially traumatic. This acknowledgement triggers a cultural shift in care for those people (McCartan, 2020; Kubiak et al., 2017). Dr Stephanie Covington's work in the field led many women's prisons across England and Wales to work to become TI (Auty et al., 2022; Kelman et al., 2024a), the success of this initiative was based on five key principles; safety, trustworthiness, choice, collaboration, and empowerment (Vaswani and Paul, 2019).

Section 4.3.1 showed that although feeling safe is rare in prison, a TI approach aims to improve this by even the simplest of things like language (Treisman, 2021). Using negative language in prison poses the risk of re-traumatising individuals, therefore training staff with TI language skills can help end this cycle (Hart et al., 2024). Section 4.3.2 found trust plays an instrumental role in staff-prisoner relationships (Waite, 2023b). Such relationships are beneficial for both prisoners and staff (Bradley, 2017; Liebling et al., 2011). Section 4.3.3 highlighted how little choice and autonomy prisoners are given (Driessen et al., 2023). Implementing TI approaches aim to improve prisoners' ability to choose, even at the simplest level (SAMHSA, 2014b). Section 4.3.4 recognised for a TI approach to become successful collaboration is essential, and everyone has their part to play even prisoners (SAMHSA, 2014a; Uglean, 2024). Section 4.3.5 discussed empowerment, highlighting how participating in TI interventions gave women a sense of belonging and helped to manage stress (Covington and Bloom, 2007; Petrillo, 2021).

Finally, this chapter discussed the practical implications of TIP, finding prison is an environment that can make BTI very hard to succeed (Miller and Najavits, 2012). To be successful would require substantial change, and this change would not be possible without large funding and strong leadership (Huo et al., 2023; Uglean, 2024). Even when both factors are present, issues such as staff turnover and overcrowding act as barriers to success because it can harm relationships essential for trauma healing (Hardan et al., 2023; Sturge, 2024).

Overall, this chapter recognises the potential benefits TIPs in prisons can bring, that would be extremely beneficial for much of the prison population with experiences of trauma. However, it also identifies the environment it is practised in needs to allow it to succeed, so fundamental change is needed for TIPs to work and flourish in prisons (Levenson and Willis, 2018).

Chapter 5: Conclusion

5.1 Findings

The first chapter provided the context of trauma, using two definitions, from SAMHSA (2014a) and Blehm (2024), the latter critiqued SAMHSA's definition for its overfocus on the effects of trauma. This chapter recognised that trauma presents itself differently in everybody, the effects can be unrecognisable to utterly destructive (Center for Substance Abuse Treatment (US), 2014b). Finally, this chapter considered the prevalence of trauma in prison; describing how prisoners, both men and women, report having experienced extremely high levels of CT on the CTQ and ACE-Q (Altintas and Bilici, 2018; Ford et al., 2020), significantly higher than those of the general population (Witt et al., 2019).

The second chapter explored prison violence and trauma, introducing a key theory the POI (Armour, 2012). This theory aims to explain why prison life can be so challenging through five deprivations: liberty, goods and services, heterosexual relationships, autonomy, and security (Shammas, 2017). This chapter discussed how behaviours described as 'maladaptive' can be the result of trauma that has been exacerbated by the deprivations that occur in the prison environment as suggested in the POI (Edgemon and Clay-Warner, 2018; Edgemon, 2016). Additionally, this chapter highlighted how staff can also experience trauma from the prison environment, from witnessing self-harm or suicide attempts to being physically assaulted at work (Bell et al., 2019; Sorensen et al., 2011).

The third chapter introduced what it means to become TI in a prison environment (McCartan, 2020; Kubiak et al., 2017), highlighting that women's prisons across England and Wales have been working towards BTI since 2015, which was based on the influential work of Dr Stephanie Covington (Auty et al., 2022). This chapter then discussed the five key principles of TIP; safety, trustworthiness, choice, collaboration, and empowerment (Vaswani and Paul, 2019), showing how improving these factors has the potential to reduce the previously discussed 'maladaptive' behaviours and prevent re-traumatisation. Finally, this chapter discussed the main barriers of TIPs that inhibit its success; lack of funding or strong leadership, staff turnover, and overcrowding (Uglean, 2024; Jewkes et al., 2019).

5.2 Answering the research questions

The overarching question of this research is can TIPs reduce the re-traumatisation of people in the prison environment?

This was answered through two underpinning questions. The first question being how does trauma manifest within prison violence and harm? This dissertation answered this by first identifying the impact trauma can have on a person, section 3.2.1 found trauma can present itself differently in everyone, in some it can be subtle but in others completely destructive (Center for Substance Abuse Treatment (US), 2014b). Acknowledging this, section 3.0 highlights prisoners' trauma can manifest itself in behaviours often seen as violent or harmful including: mental health, drug-use, self-harm, self-inflicted death, and inmate-on-inmate assaults. Sections 3.2 and 3.3 discuss these behaviours as the result of pre-existing factors that get exacerbated by the depriving prison environment, such as individuals with experiences of trauma becoming re-traumatised in the depriving prison environment (Dye, 2010).

The second research question is to what extent can TIPs enhance support for prisoners and staff? To answer this question the research explored whether TIPs could alleviate some of the deprivation felt by prisoners, it did this by identifying the potential benefits and barriers to its success. As section 3.2.1 highlighted, prison is an environment with extreme levels of deprivation that can become the place of re-traumatisation (Haney, 2012; Crole-Rees et al., 2024), TIPs aim to alleviate the deprivation and prevent re-traumatisation by focussing on improving safety, trustworthiness, choice, collaboration, and empowerment for prisoners and staff. This could even be from the smallest things like the language used when speaking to prisoners (Treisman, 2021) or giving prisoners more of a choice in their therapeutic care (SAMHSA, 2014b). Section 4.4 discussed funding, leadership, staff turnover, and overcrowding as practical implications (Uglean, 2024; Jewkes et al., 2019). Establishing TIPs can work well, but they must be implemented in an environment that allows them to flourish, not an environment that has little funding, a weak leadership team, staff who leave their post within three years, or prisons running over capacity as it risks successful training and positive relationships (Levenson and Willis, 2018; Uglean, 2024; Prison Reform Trust, 2022; Sturge, 2024).

Therefore, in terms of answering the overarching research question, this dissertation argues TIPs do have the potential to reduce re-traumatising people in prison, but not without radical change to the prisons organisational culture and policy (Malik et al., 2021).

5.3 Future directions

5.3.1 Practice

Implementing TIPs has developed a negative narrative in the prison setting from many scholars who rightly point out the fact it is not working as well as research by Dr Stephanie Covington (Chief Inspector

of Prisons, 2025; Kelman et al., 2024b). This dissertation argues the fault is not with the practice itself, but the way in which its implemented (Levenson and Willis, 2018). Future directions for TIPs in prisons should first focus on reducing staff turnover, as found in section 4.4, staff turnover is of significant concern for the success of applying TIPs in prison, from the prison officers that left the service last year, 50% had been in the role for less than three years, and 26% less than one year (Prison Reform Trust, 2022). These high rates of staff turnover threaten effective BTI training and positive staff-prisoner relationships, as found in section 4.4 these are essential for the success of TIPs (Hardan et al., 2023; Schultz et al., 2016). For successful future practice there must be radical change to allow TIPs to have the greatest success, how can one expect TIPs to thrive in prison when the environment does not allow it to do so?

5.3.2 Policy

Future directions for policy could focus on requiring mandatory reviews of how TIPs are running in prisons in England and Wales. These reviews would add to the well-established work of the Farmer review and The Female Offender Strategy, aiming to continue to help support individuals who are living in prison and aim to keep prison as a last resort, to avoid re-traumatisation (Farmer 2019; Ministry of Justice, 2018). The potential benefits these reviews could offer would be extremely important for the well-being of prisoners and staff, ensuring the staff working in the prison continue to take on each value of TIP. The reviews would also share important information to policy makers and researchers on certain aspects that may need improving or further attention.

5.3.3 Academia

In terms of future directions for academics, the focus of research should be centred around why TIPs are not working. Why are prisons that implement TIPs not caring for prisoners' basic needs, and the sheer amount of distress felt by the female prisoners in England and Wales is causing them to self-harm (Chief Inspector of Prisons, 2025). Why in TI prisons are the prisoners not seeing a positive change in staff attitudes and behaviours after BTI training has occurred (Kelman et al., 2024b). Further research into why these issues remain prevalent after BTI training has occurred will aid researchers to ensure future implementation succeeds.

References

Al-Rousan, T., Rubenstein, L., Sieleni, B., Deol, H. and Wallace, R. B. (2017) Inside the Nation's Largest Mental Health Institution: A Prevalence Study in a State Prison System. *BMC Public Health*. [Online]. 17 (1) April. Available from: <<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s12889-017-4257-0>> [Accessed 12 November 2024].

Alhojailan, M. I. (2012) *Thematic Analysis: A Critical Review of Its Process and Evaluation*. [Online]. Available from: <<https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&type=pdf&doi=0c66700a0f4b4a0626f87a3692d4f34e599c4d0e>> [Accessed 21 February 2025].

Altintas, M. and Bilici, M. (2018) Evaluation of Childhood Trauma with Respect to Criminal Behavior, Dissociative Experiences, Adverse Family Experiences and Psychiatric Backgrounds among Prison Inmates. *Comprehensive Psychiatry*. [Online]. 82 (1) April, pp. 100–107. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comppsy.2017.12.006>> [Accessed 31 January 2025].

Armour, C. (2012) Mental Health in Prison: A Trauma Perspective on Importation and Deprivation. *International Journal of Criminology and Sociological Theory*. [Online]. 5 (2) July, pp. 886–894. Available from: <<https://ijcst.journals.yorku.ca/index.php/ijcst/article/view/35703/32435>> [Accessed 12 November 2024].

Augsburger, A., Neri, C., Bodenmann, P., Gravier, B., Jaquier, V. and Clair, C. (2022) Assessing Incarcerated Women's Physical and Mental Health Status and Needs in a Swiss Prison: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Health & Justice*. [Online]. 10 (1) February. Available from: <<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s40352-022-00171-z>> [Accessed 13 November 2024].

Auty, K. M., Liebling, A., Schliehe, A. and Crewe, B. (2022) What Is Trauma-Informed Practice? Towards Operationalisation of the Concept in Two Prisons for Women. *Criminology & Criminal Justice*. [Online]. 23 (5) May, pp. 716–738. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/17488958221094980>> [Accessed 6 January 2025].

Baggio, S., Gétaz, L., Tran, N. T., Peigné, N., Chacowry Pala, K., Golay, D., Heller, P., Bodenmann, P. and Wolff, H. (2018) Association of Overcrowding and Turnover with SelfHarm in a Swiss Pre-Trial Prison. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. [Online]. 15 (4) April, p. 601. Available from: <<https://www.mdpi.com/16604601/15/4/601>> [Accessed 21 November 2024].

Baldwin, L. (2018) Motherhood Disrupted: Reflections of Post- Prison Mothers. *Emotion, Space and Society*. [Online]. 26 February, pp. 49–56. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emospa.2017.02.002>> [Accessed 17 November 2024].

Barry, C. (2017) ‘You Just Get on with the Job’: Prison Officers’ Experiences of Deaths in Custody in the Irish Prison Service. *Prison Service Journal*. [Online]. 56 (1) March, p. 304309. Available from: <<https://shura.shu.ac.uk/21409/7/Barry-YouJustGetOnWithIt.pdf>> [Accessed 27 November 2024].

Bell, S., Hopkin, G. and Forrester, A. (2019) Exposure to Traumatic Events and the Experience of Burnout, Compassion Fatigue and Compassion Satisfaction among Prison Mental Health Staff: An Exploratory Survey. *Issues in Mental Health Nursing*. [Online]. 40 (4) February, pp. 304–309. Available from: <http://eprints.lse.ac.uk/90452/1/Hopkin__exposure-to-traumatic-events.pdf> [Accessed 26 November 2024].

Benedict, A. and CORE Associates (2014) *Using Trauma-Informed Practices to Enhance Safety and Security in Women’s Correctional Facilities*. [Online]. Available from: <<https://bja.ojp.gov/sites/g/files/xyckuh186/files/Publications/NRCJIWUsingTraumaInformedPractices.pdf>> [Accessed 5 January 2025].

Bierie, D. M. (2010) The Impact of Prison Conditions on Staff Well-Being. *International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology*. [Online]. 56 (1) November, pp. 81–95. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/0306624X10388383>> [Accessed 27 November 2024].

Blehm, A. (2024) What Is Trauma? A Critique and Definition. *Journal of theoretical and philosophical psychology*. [Online]. May. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1037/teo0000274>> [Accessed 7 October 2024].

Bradley, A. (2017) *Trauma-Informed Practice: Exploring the Role of Adverse Life Experiences on the Behaviour of Offenders and the Effectiveness of Associated Criminal Justice Strategies* [Doctoral Thesis]. Northumbria University. Available from:

<https://eprints.leedsbeckett.ac.uk/id/eprint/5460/1/Trauma-Informed%20PracticePhDAB.pdf>
[Accessed 9 January 2025].

Bradley, A. (2021) Viewing Her Majesty's Prison Service through a Trauma-Informed Lens. *Prison Service Journal*. [Online]. 255. Available from:
<<https://eprints.leedsbeckett.ac.uk/id/eprint/7846/1/ViewingHerMajestysPrisonServiceThroughTraumaInformedLensPV-BRADLEY.pdf>> [Accessed 12 January 2025].

Breuer, E., Remond, M., Lighton, S., Passalacqua, J., Galouzis, J., Stewart, K.-A. and Sullivan, E. (2021) The Needs and Experiences of Mothers While in Prison and Post-Release: A Rapid Review and Thematic Synthesis. *Health & Justice*. [Online]. 9 (31) November. Available from:
<<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40352-021-00153-7>> [Accessed 17 November 2024].

Brezean, I., Moldovan, H., Ferechide, D., Vilcu, M. and Petrea, S. (2016) Self-Harm in the Prison System. *Romanian Journal of Legal Medicine*. [Online]. 24 (3) October, pp. 194–198. Available from:
<<http://www.rjlm.ro/system/revista/39/194-198.pdf>> [Accessed 21 November 2024].

Briere, J., Kaltman, S. and Green, B. L. (2008) Accumulated Childhood Trauma and Symptom Complexity. *Journal of Traumatic Stress*. [Online]. 21 (2), pp. 223–226. Available from:
<<https://doi.org/10.1002/jts.20317>> [Accessed 9 November 2024].

Bukten, A. and Stavseth, M. R. (2021) Suicide in Prison and after Release: A 17-Year National Cohort Study. *European Journal of Epidemiology*. [Online]. 36 (10) August, pp. 1075–1083. Available from:
<<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10654-021-00782-0>> [Accessed 22 November 2024].

Busch, B. and McNamara, T. (2020) Language and Trauma: An Introduction. *Applied Linguistics*. [Online]. 41 (3) April, pp. 323–333. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/amaa002>>
[Accessed 29 January 2025].

Cao, L., Zhao, J. and Van Dine, S. (1997) Prison Disciplinary Tickets: A Test of the Deprivation and Importation Models. *Journal of Criminal Justice*. [Online]. 25 (2) January, pp. 103–113. Available from:
<[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0047-2352\(96\)00054-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0047-2352(96)00054-2)> [Accessed 12 November 2024].

Center for Substance Abuse Treatment (US) (2014a) *Trauma-Informed Care in Behavioral*

Health Services. [Online]. Rockville MD: Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration (US). Available from: <<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK207192/>> [Accessed 9 November 2024].

Center for Substance Abuse Treatment (US) (2014b) *Understanding the Impact of Trauma*. [Online]. Rockville, United States: Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration (US). Available from: <<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK207191/?report=printable>> [Accessed 14 October 2024].

Cesaroni, C., Maycock, M. and Vaswani, N. (2023) Prison Masculinities, Trauma and Incarcerated Young Men. *Men and Masculinities*. [Online]. 26 (2) April, p. 1097184X2311666. Available from: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369832618_Prison_Masculinities_Trauma_and_Incarcerated_Young_Men> [Accessed 13 January 2025].

Chief Inspector of Prisons (2025) *Frustrations about a Lack of Basic Care Lead Women in Prison to Self-Harm – HM Inspectorate of Prisons*. [Online]. Justiceinspectorates.gov.uk. Available from: <<https://hmiprisons.justiceinspectorates.gov.uk/news/frustrations-about-alack-of-basic-care-leads-women-in-prison-to-self-harm/>> [Accessed 12 February 2025].

Ciurria, M. (2018) The Loss of Autonomy in Abused Persons: Psychological, Moral, and Legal Dimensions. *Humanities*. [Online]. 7 (2) May, p. 48. Available from: <<https://www.mdpi.com/2076-0787/7/2/48/htm>> [Accessed 30 January 2025].

Clarke, V. and Braun, V. (2016) Thematic Analysis. *The Journal of Positive Psychology*. [Online]. 12 (3) December, pp. 297–298. Available from: <<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/17439760.2016.1262613#d1e121>> [Accessed 21 February 2025].

Classen, C. C., Palesh, O. G. and Aggarwal, R. (2005) Sexual Revictimization. *Trauma, Violence, & Abuse*. [Online]. 6 (2) April, pp. 103–129. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/1524838005275087>> [Accessed 9 November 2024].

Clements-Nolle, K., Wolden, M. and Bargmann-Losche, J. (2009) Childhood Trauma and Risk

for Past and Future Suicide Attempts among Women in Prison. *Women's Health Issues*. [Online]. 19 (3) May, pp. 185–192. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.whi.2009.02.002>> [Accessed 22 November 2024].

Constantian, M. B. (2019) *Childhood Abuse, Body Shame, and Addictive Plastic Surgery*. [Online]. New York: Routledge, pp. 195–236. Available from: <<https://www.taylorfrancis.com/leedsbeckett.idm.oclc.org/books/oa-mono/10.4324/9781315657721/childhood-abuse-body-shame-addictive-plastic-surgery/mark-constantian>> [Accessed 7 October 2024].

Cope, N. (2003) 'It's No Time or High Time': Young Offenders' Experiences of Time and Drug Use in Prison. *The Howard Journal of Criminal Justice*. [Online]. 42 (2) May, pp. 158–175. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2311.t01-1-00273>> [Accessed 18 November 2024].

Covington, S. (2001) Helping Women Recover: Creating Gender-Responsive Treatment. [Online]. In: Straussner, S. L. A. and Brown, S. eds. *The Handbook of Addiction Treatment for Women: Theory and Practice*. United Kingdom: John Wiley & Sons. Available from: <<https://www.centerforgenderandjustice.org/site/assets/files/1537/5.pdf>> [Accessed 31 October 2024].

Covington, S. (2022) Creating a Trauma-Informed Justice System for Women Definitions of Trauma Sensitive, Trauma Informed, Trauma Responsive, and Trauma Specific. [Online]. In: Brown, S. L. and Gelsthorpe, L. eds. *The Wiley Handbook on What Works with Girls and Women in Conflict with the Law: A Critical Review of Theory, Practice, and Policy*. United Kingdom: John Wiley & Sons, pp. 172–184. Available from: <https://www.stephaniecovington.com/site/assets/files/1513/creating_a_traumainformed_justice_system_for_women_website_version.pdf> [Accessed 31 October 2024].

Covington, S. S. and Bloom, B. E. (2007) Gender Responsive Treatment and Services in Correctional Settings. *Women & Therapy*. [Online]. 29 (3–4) April, pp. 9–33. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1300/J015v29n03_02> [Accessed 9 January 2025].

Crawley, E. M. (2013) *Doing Prison Work*. [Online]. Routledge. Available from: <<https://r1.vlereader.com/EpubReader?ean=1781135991746#>> [Accessed 27 November 2024].

Crewe, B., Hulley, S. and Wright, S. (2017) The Gendered Pains of Life Imprisonment. *British Journal of Criminology*. [Online]. 57 (6) January, pp. 1359–1378. Available from: <<https://academic.oup.com/bjc/article/57/6/1359/2877142>> [Accessed 18 November 2024].

Crewe, B., Schliehe, A. and Przybylska, D. A. (2022) ‘It Causes a Lot of Problems’: Relational Ambiguities and Dynamics between Prisoners and Staff in a Women’s Prison. *European Journal of Criminology*. [Online]. 20 (3) December, pp. 925–946. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/14773708221140870>> [Accessed 4 February 2025].

Crole-Rees, C., Tomlin, J., Kalebic, N., Argent, S., Berrington, C., Chaplin, E., Davies, J., Hoskins, M., James, L., Jarrett, M., John, O., Jones, L., Kothari, R., Kretzschmar, I., MacManus, D., Martin, M., McKinnon, I., O’Connor, G., Petrillo, M. and Phillips, M. (2024) An Optimal Trauma-Informed Pathway for PTSD, Complex PTSD and Other Mental Health and Psychosocial Impacts of Trauma in Prisons: An Expert Consensus Statement. *Psychology Crime and Law*. [Online]. September, pp. 1–22. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/1068316X.2024.2394807>> [Accessed 12 November 2024].

Crole-Rees, C., Tomlin, J., Kalebic, N., Collings, M., Roberts, N. P. and Forrester, A. (2023) An Exploration of Staff Views of a Trauma-Informed Pathway in a Sentenced and Remand Prison. *Journal of forensic practice*. [Online]. 25 (4) October, pp. 420–436. Available from: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/374696648_An_exploration_of_staff_views_of_a_trauma-informed_pathway_in_a_sentenced_and_remand_prison> [Accessed 13 January 2025].

DeLisi, M., Berg, M. T. and Hochstetler, A. (2004) Gang Members, Career Criminals and Prison Violence: Further Specification of the Importation Model of Inmate Behavior. *Criminal Justice Studies*. [Online]. 17 (4) December, pp. 369–383. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/1478601042000314883>> [Accessed 14 November 2024].

DiBennardo, R. A. (2018) Ideal Victims and Monstrous Offenders: How the News Media Represent Sexual Predators. *Socius: Sociological Research for a Dynamic World*. [Online]. 4 (4) January, p. 237802311880251. Available from: <<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/2378023118802512>> [Accessed 29 October 2024].

Driessen, J. M. A., Dirkzwager, A., Harte, J. M. and Aarts, H. (2023) How Restrictions of Choice Affect the Sense of Agency: The Case of Personal Autonomy in Prison. *Journal of criminal psychology*. [Online]. 13 (4) August, pp. 381–393. Available from:

<<https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/jcp-12-2022-0035/full/html>> [Accessed 30 January 2025].

Duggins, C. (2024) *Understanding Lived Experiences of Correctional Officers' Reintegration Back into the Work Environment Post-Assault* [Doctoral Dissertation]. Liberty University. Available from: <<https://digitalcommons.liberty.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=6159&context=doctoral>> [Accessed 29 November 2024].

Dunn, E. C., Nishimi, K., Powers, A. and Bradley, B. (2017) Is Developmental Timing of Trauma Exposure Associated with Depressive and Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder Symptoms in Adulthood? *Journal of Psychiatric Research*. [Online]. 84 (84) January, pp. 119–127. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychires.2016.09.004>> [Accessed 29 October 2024].

Dye, H. (2018) The Impact and Long-Term Effects of Childhood Trauma. *Journal of Human Behavior in the Social Environment*. [Online]. 28 (3), pp. 381–392. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/10911359.2018.1435328>> [Accessed 9 November 2024].

Dye, M. H. (2010) Deprivation, Importation, and Prison Suicide: Combined Effects of Institutional Conditions and Inmate Composition. *Journal of Criminal Justice*. [Online]. 38 (4) July, pp. 796–806. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcrimjus.2010.05.007>> [Accessed 13 November 2024].

Eckes, A. and Radunovich, H. L. (2007) Trauma and Adolescents. *EDIS*. [Online]. 2007 (20) November. Available from: <<https://sfyl.ifas.ufl.edu/media/sfylifasufledu/duval/fcs/Traumaand-Adolescents.pdf>> [Accessed 17 October 2024].

Edgemon, T. (2016) *Inmate Mental Health: Importation, Deprivation, and Integrated Perspectives* [Masters]. The University of Georgia. Available from: <https://getd.libs.uga.edu/pdfs/edgemon_timothy_g_201612_ma.pdf> [Accessed 23 December 2024].

Edgemon, T. G. and Clay-Warner, J. (2018) Inmate Mental Health and the Pains of Imprisonment. *Society and Mental Health*. [Online]. 9 (1) August, pp. 33–50. Available from: <<https://doi-org.leedsbeckett.idm.oclc.org/10.1177/2156869318785424>> [Accessed 22 January 2025].

Elwood, L. S., Mott, J., Lohr, J. M. and Galovski, T. E. (2011) Secondary Trauma Symptoms in Clinicians: A Critical Review of the Construct, Specificity, and Implications for Trauma Focused Treatment. *Clinical Psychology Review*. [Online]. 31 (1) February, pp. 25–36. available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2010.09.004>> [Accessed 27 November 2024].

Farmer, L. (2019) *The Importance of Strengthening Female Offenders' Family and Other Relationships to Prevent Reoffending and Reduce Intergenerational Crime*. [Online]. Ministry of Justice. Available from: <<https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5d078d37e5274a0b879394c7/farmerreview-women.PDF>> [Accessed 9 March 2025].

Favril, L., Yu, R., Hawton, K. and Fazel, S. (2020) Risk Factors for Self-Harm in Prison: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *The Lancet Psychiatry*. [Online]. 7 (8) August, pp. 682–691. Available from: <[https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanpsy/article/PIIS22150366\(20\)30190-5/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanpsy/article/PIIS22150366(20)30190-5/fulltext)> [Accessed 21 November 2024].

Fazel, S., Cartwright, J., Psych, M., Norman-Nott, A. and Hawton, K. (2008) Suicide in Prisoners: A Review of Risk Factors. *Mental Health National Health Service (NHS) Foundation Trust*. [Online]. 69 (11), pp. 1721–1731. Available from: <https://www.psychiatrist.com/wpcontent/uploads/2021/02/18009_suicide-prisoners-systematic-review-risk-factors.pdf> [Accessed 22 November 2024].

Ford, K., Bellis, M. A., Hughes, K., Barton, E. R. and Newbury, A. (2020) Adverse Childhood Experiences: A Retrospective Study to Understand Their Associations with Lifetime Mental Health Diagnosis, Self-Harm or Suicide Attempt, and Current Low Mental Wellbeing in a Male Welsh Prison Population. *Health & Justice*. [Online]. 8 (1) June. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40352-020-00115-5>> [Accessed 31 January 2025].

Frankel, J. B. (1998) Ferenczi's Trauma Theory. *The American Journal of Psychoanalysis*. [Online]. 58 (1), pp. 41–61. Available from: <<https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1023/A:1022522031707>> [Accessed 8 October 2024].

Frühwald, S. and Frottier, P. (2005) Suicide in Prison. *The Lancet*. [Online]. 366 (9493) October, pp. 1242–1244. Available from: <[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(05\)673278](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(05)673278)> [Accessed 22 November 2024].

Gates, M., Turney, A., Ferguson, E., Walker, V. and Staples-Horne, M. (2017) Associations among Substance Use, Mental Health Disorders, and Self-Harm in a Prison Population: Examining Group Risk for Suicide Attempt. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. [Online]. 14 (3) March, p. 317. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph14030317>> [Accessed 21 November 2024].

Gillespie, W. (2005) A Multilevel Model of Drug Abuse inside Prison. *The Prison Journal*. [Online]. 85 (2) June, pp. 223–246. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/0032885505277002>> [Accessed 18 November 2024].

Goodstein, L., Mackenzie, D. L. and Shotland, R. L. (1984) Personal Control and Inmate Adjustment to Prison. *Criminology*. [Online]. 22 (3) August, pp. 343–369. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-9125.1984.tb00304.x>> [Accessed 30 January 2025].

Goomany, A. and Dickinson, T. (2015) The Influence of Prison Climate on the Mental Health of Adult Prisoners: A Literature Review. *Journal of Psychiatric and Mental Health Nursing*. [Online]. 22 (6) June, pp. 413–422. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1111/jpm.12231>> [Accessed 18 November 2024].

Goyes, D. R. (2024) Trauma and Imported Vulnerability in Prison Suicides. *Punishment & Society*. [Online]. November. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/14624745241295499>> [Accessed 22 November 2024].

Haggerty, K. D. and Bucierius, S. (2020) The Proliferating Pains of Imprisonment. *Incarceration*. [Online]. 1 (1) July. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/2632666320936432>> [Accessed 20 January 2025].

Haney, C. (2012) Prison Effects in the Era of Mass Incarceration. *The Prison Journal*. [Online]. 19 (3) July, pp. 1–24. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/0032885512448604>> [Accessed 18 November 2024].

Haney, C. (2017) ‘Madness’ and Penal Confinement: Some Observations on Mental Illness and Prison Pain. *Punishment & Society*. [Online]. 19 (3) April, pp. 310–326. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/1462474517705389>> [Accessed 18 November 2024].

Hardan, T., Bosk, E. A., Mendez, A., Williams-Butler, A., Julien, F. and MacKenzie, M. J. (2023) A Relational Workforce Capacity Approach to Trauma-Informed Care Implementation: Staff Rejection Sensitivity as a Potential Barrier to Organizational Attachment. *Behavioral sciences*. [Online]. 13 (8) August, pp. 652–652. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.3390/bs13080652>> [Accessed 14 January 2025].

Harner, H. M. and Riley, S. (2013) The Impact of Incarceration on Women’s Mental Health. *Qualitative Health Research*. [Online]. 23 (1) October, pp. 26–42. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732312461452>> [Accessed 18 November 2024].

Hart, L., Bliton, J. N., Castater, C., Beard, J. H. and Smith, R. N. (2024) Trauma-Informed Language as a Tool for Health Equity. *Trauma Surgery & Acute Care Open*. [Online]. 9 (1) December, p. e001558. Available from: <<https://tsaco.bmj.com/content/tsaco/9/1/e001558.full.pdf>> [Accessed 29 January 2025].

Hawton, K., Linsell, L., Adeniji, T., Sariaslan, A. and Fazel, S. (2014) Self-Harm in Prisons in England and Wales: An Epidemiological Study of Prevalence, Risk Factors, Clustering, and Subsequent Suicide. *The Lancet*. [Online]. 383 (9923) March, pp. 1147–1154. Available from: <<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3978651/>> [Accessed 21 November 2024].

Haynal, A. (2014) Trauma—Revisited: Ferenczi and Modern Psychoanalysis. *Psychoanalytic Inquiry*. [Online]. 34 (2) February, pp. 98–111. Available from: <<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/epdf/10.1080/07351690.2014.850272?needAccess=true>> [Accessed 9 October 2024].

Heide, K. M. and Solomon, E. P. (2006) Biology, Childhood Trauma, and Murder: Rethinking Justice. *International Journal of Law and Psychiatry*. [Online]. 29 (3) May, pp. 220–233. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijlp.2005.10.001>> [Accessed 8 October 2024].

House of Commons (2021) *Mental Health in Prison Fifth Report of Session 2021-22 Report, Together with Formal Minutes Relating to the Report*. [Online]. Available from: <<https://committees.parliament.uk/publications/7455/documents/78054/default/>> [Accessed 18 November 2024].

House of Commons Justice Committee (2022) *Women in Prison*. [Online]. Available from: <<https://committees.parliament.uk/publications/23269/documents/169738/default/>> [Accessed 17 November 2024].

Huo, Y., Couzner, L., Windsor, T., Laver, K., Dissanayaka, N. N. and Cations, M. (2023) Barriers and Enablers for the Implementation of Trauma-Informed Care in Healthcare Settings: A Systematic Review. *Implementation Science Communications*. [Online]. 4 (1) May, p. 49. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1186/s43058-023-00428-0>> [Accessed 14 January 2025].

Jesson, J. and Lacey, F. (2006) How to Do (or Not to Do) a Critical Literature Review. *Pharmacy Education*. [Online]. 6 (2) June, pp. 139–148. Available from: <https://publications.aston.ac.uk/id/eprint/3431/1/Jesson_and_lacey2006.pdf> [Accessed 21 February 2025].

Jewkes, Y., Jordan, M., Wright, S. and Bendelow, G. (2019) Designing ‘Healthy’ Prisons for Women: Incorporating Trauma-Informed Care and Practice (TICP) into Prison Planning and Design. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. [Online]. 16 (20) October. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16203818>> [Accessed 7 January 2025].

Johnson, N. S. (2017) *Secondary Traumatic Stress, Compassion Fatigue, and Burnout: How Working in Correctional Settings Affects Mental Health Providers* [Doctoral Dissertation]. Antioch University. Available from: <https://etd.ohiolink.edu/acprod/odb_etd/etd/r/1501/10?clear=10&p10_accession_num=antioch1477328356041575> [Accessed 27 November 2024].

Kaap-Deeder, J. van der, Audenaert, E., Vandeveldde, S., Soenens, B., Van Mastrigt, S., Mabbe, E. and Vansteenkiste, M. (2017) Choosing When Choices Are Limited: The Role of Perceived Afforded Choice and Autonomy in Prisoners’ Well-Being. *Law and Human Behavior* [Online], 41 (6) December, pp. 567–578. Available from: <<https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/lhb0000259>> [Accessed 24 January 2025].

Keena, L. D., Lambert, E. G., Haynes, S. H., May, D. and Doty, P. A. (2022) Testing the Job Demands-Resources Model with Organizational Trust among Prison Staff. *Criminal Justice Review*. [Online]. 47 (2) February, p. 073401682210767. Available from:

<<https://doi.org/leedsbeckett.idm.oclc.org/10.1177/07340168221076789>> [Accessed 27 November 2024].

Kelman, J., Palmer, L., Gribble, R. and MacManus, D. (2024a) Prison Officers' Perceptions of Delivering Trauma-Informed Care in Women's Prisons. *Journal of Aggression Maltreatment & Trauma*. [Online]. 33 (10) June, pp. 1–22. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/10926771.2024.2371860>> [Accessed 6 January 2025].

Kelman, J., Palmer, L., Gribble, R. and MacManus, D. (2024b) Time and Care: A Qualitative Exploration of Prisoners' Perceptions of Trauma-Informed Care in Women's Prisons. *International Journal of Forensic Mental Health* [Online], 23 (4) January, pp. 1–12. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/14999013.2023.2298484>> [Accessed 8 January 2025].

Kenning, C., Cooper, J., Short, V., Shaw, J., Abel, K. and Chew-Graham, C. (2010) Prison Staff and Women Prisoner's Views on Self-Harm; Their Implications for Service Delivery and Development: A Qualitative Study. *Criminal Behaviour and Mental Health*. [Online]. 20 (4) July, pp. 274–284. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1002/cbm.777>> [Accessed 21 November 2024].

King, E. A. (2015) Outcomes of Trauma-Informed Interventions for Incarcerated Women. *International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology*. [Online]. 61 (6) September, pp. 667–688. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/0306624X15603082>> [Accessed 9 January 2025].

Koenen, K. C., Roberts, A., Stone, D. and Dunn, E. (2011) The Epidemiology of Early Childhood Trauma. [Online]. In: Lanius, R. A., Vermetten, E. and Pain, C. eds., *The Impact of Early Life Trauma on Health and Disease the Hidden Epidemic*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, pp. 13–24. Available from:

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Andrea_Roberts2/publication/286713984_The_epidemiology_of_early_childhood_trauma/links/5670751108ae0d8b0cc0efda/Theepidemiology-of-early-childhood-trauma.pdf> [Accessed 17 October 2024].

Kolaitis, G. and Olf, M. (2017) Psychotraumatology in Greece. *European Journal of Psychotraumatology*. [Online]. 8 (4) July, p. 135175. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/20008198.2017.1351757>> [Accessed 7 October 2024].

Kolind, T. and Duke, K. (2016) Drugs in Prisons: Exploring Use, Control, Treatment and Policy. *Drugs: Education, Prevention and Policy*. [Online]. 23 (2) March, pp. 89–92. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.3109/09687637.2016.1153604>> [Accessed 18 November 2024].

Krupnik, V. (2018) Trauma or Adversity? *Traumatology*. [Online]. 25 (4) August. Available from: <<http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/trm0000169>> [Accessed 17 October 2024].

Kubiak, S., Covington, S. and Hillier, C. (2017) Trauma-Informed Corrections. [Online]. In: Springer, D. and Roberts, A. eds., *Social Work in Juvenile and Criminal Justice System*. Springfield, IL: Charles C Thomas Publisher. Available from: <https://mronline.org/wpcontent/uploads/2018/01/Trauma20Informed20Corrections20Kubiak_Covington_Hillier202017.pdf> [Accessed 5 January 2025].

Kupermann, D. (2022) Social Trauma and Testimony: A Reading of Maryan S. Maryan's Notebooks Inspired by Sándor Ferenczi. *The American Journal of Psychoanalysis*. [Online]. 82 (2) June, pp. 268–280. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1057/s11231-022-09354-x>> [Accessed 9 October 2024].

Lambert, E. G., Hogan, N. L., Moore, B., Tucker, K., Jenkins, M., Stevenson, M. and Jiang, S. (2009) The Impact of the Work Environment on Prison Staff: The Issue of Consideration, Structure, Job Variety, and Training. *American Journal of Criminal Justice*. [Online]. 34 (3–4) March, pp. 166–180. Available from: <<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12103009-9062-6>> [Accessed 26 November 2024].

Leban, L., Cardwell, S. M., Copes, H. and Brezina, T. (2015) Adapting to Prison Life: A Qualitative Examination of the Coping Process among Incarcerated Offenders. *Justice Quarterly*. [Online]. 33 (6) February, pp. 943–969. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/07418825.2015.1012096>> [Accessed 18 November 2024].

Levan, K. (2016) *Prison Violence*. [Online]. London: Routledge. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315602189>> [Accessed 22 November 2024].

Levenson, J. S. and Willis, G. M. (2018) Implementing Trauma-Informed Care in Correctional Treatment and Supervision. *Journal of Aggression, Maltreatment & Trauma*. [Online]. 28 (4) October, pp. 1–21. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/10926771.2018.1531959>> [Accessed 6 January 2025].

Liebling, A., Price, D. and Schefer, G. (2011) *The Prison Officer*. [Online]. New York: Routledge. Available from: <<https://r4.vlereader.com/EpubReader?ean=1780203832998#>> [Accessed 13 January 2025].

Listwan, S. J., Sullivan, C. J., Agnew, R., Cullen, F. T. and Colvin, M. (2013) The Pains of Imprisonment Revisited: The Impact of Strain on Inmate Recidivism. *Justice Quarterly*. [Online]. 30 (1) February, pp. 144–168. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/07418825.2011.597772>> [Accessed 22 January 2025].

Malik, N., Facer-Irwin, E., Dickson, H., Bird, A. and MacManus, D. (2021) The Effectiveness of Trauma-Focused Interventions in Prison Settings: A Systematic Review and MetaAnalysis. *Trauma, Violence, & Abuse*. [Online]. 24 (2) October, p. 152483802110438. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/15248380211043890>> [Accessed 24 January 2025].

Marris, W. (2023) *Trauma-Informed Workplaces*. [Online]. Campaign for Trauma Informed Policy and Practice. Available from: <<https://www.ctipp.org/post/toolkit-trauma-informedworkplaces>> [Accessed 14 January 2025].

McCartan, K. F. (2020) *Trauma-Informed Practice*. [Online]. HM Inspectorate of Probation, p. 8. Available from: <<https://www.justiceinspectrates.gov.uk/hmiprobation/wpcontent/uploads/sites/5/2020/07/Academic-Insights-McCartan.pdf>> [Accessed 5 January 2025].

McMinn, L. E., Akerman, G. and Gaffney, E. (2023) Healing Trauma in a Traumatizing Environment with Young Adult Men. *Journal of Men's Health*. [Online]. October. Available from: <<http://dx.doi.org/10.22514/jomh.2023.>> [Accessed 13 January 2025].

McNeeley, S. (2021) Situational Risk Factors for Inmate-On-Staff Assaults. *The Prison Journal*. [Online]. 27 (1–2) April, p. 003288552110104. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/00328855211010478>> [Accessed 27 November 2024].

Menschner, C. and Maul, A. (2016) *Key Ingredients for Successful Trauma-Informed Care Implementation*. [Online]. Center for Health Care Strategies, pp. 1–12. Available from: <https://www.samhsa.gov/sites/default/files/programs_campaigns/childrens_mental_health/atc-whitepaper-040616.pdf> [Accessed 14 January 2025].

Messina, N. and Calhoun, S. (2020) Efficacy of a Trauma Intervention for Women in a Security Housing Unit. *Archives of Women Health and Care*. [Online]. 3 (4) July. Available from: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343725672_Efficacy_of_a_Trauma_Intervention_for_Women_in_a_Security_Housing_Unit> [Accessed 7 January 2025].

Mignon, S. I. and Ransford, P. (2012) Mothers in Prison: Maintaining Connections with Children. *Social Work in Public Health*. [Online]. 27 (1–2) January, pp. 69–88. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/19371918.2012.630965>> [Accessed 13 November 2024].

Miller, N. A. and Najavits, L. M. (2012) Creating Trauma-Informed Correctional Care: A Balance of Goals and Environment. *European Journal of Psychotraumatology*. [Online]. 3 (1) March, p. 17246. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.3402/ejpt.v3i0.17246>> [Accessed 5 January 2025].

Ministry of Justice (2018) *Female Offender Strategy*. [Online]. Available from: <<https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5b3349c4e5274a55d7a54abe/femaleoffender-strategy.pdf>> [Accessed 9 March 2025].

Ministry of Justice (2025) Safety in Custody Statistics, England and Wales: Deaths in Prison Custody to December 2024 Assaults and Self-Harm to September 2024. [Online]. GOV.UK. Available from: <<https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/safety-in-custody-quarterlyupdate-to-september-2024/safety-in-custody-statistics-england-and-wales-deaths-in-prisoncustody-to-december-2024-assaults-and-self-harm-to-september-2024>> [Accessed 19 February 2025].

Mitchell, S. (2024) The Gendered Trauma Trajectories of Mothers Entering Prison. *Probation Journal*. [Online]. October. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/02645505241269159>> [Accessed 13 November 2024].

Norman, C. (2022) A Global Review of Prison Drug Smuggling Routes and Trends in the Usage of Drugs in Prisons. *WIREs Forensic Science*. [Online]. 5 (2) November. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1002/wfs2.1473>> [Accessed 18 November 2024].

Norman, R. E., Byambaa, M., De, R., Butchart, A., Scott, J. and Vos, T. (2012) The Long-Term Health Consequences of Child Physical Abuse, Emotional Abuse, and Neglect: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *PLoS Medicine*. [Online]. 9 (11) November, p. e1001349. Available from:

<<https://journals.plos.org/plosmedicine/article?id=10.1371/journal.pmed.1001349>> [Accessed 8 October 2024].

Nurse, J., Woodcock, P. and Ormsby, J. (2003) Influence of Environmental Factors on Mental Health within Prisons: Focus Group Study. *BMJ*. [Online]. 327 (7413) August. Available from: <<https://www.bmj.com/content/327/7413/480.short>> [Accessed 18 November 2024].

O'Hagan, A. and Hardwick, R. (2017) Behind Bars: The Truth about Drugs in Prisons. *Forensic Research & Criminology International Journal*. [Online]. 5 (3) September. Available from: <https://irep.ntu.ac.uk/id/eprint/31877/1/PubSub9284_O%27Hagan.pdf> [Accessed 18 November 2024].

Office for National Statistics (2023) Drug-Related Deaths and Suicide in Prison Custody in England and Wales - Office for National Statistics. [Online]. Available from: <<https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/birthsdeathsandmarriages/deaths/articles/drugrelateddeathsandsuicideinprisoncustodyinenglandandwales/2023-01-26>> [Accessed 18 November 2024].

Pelissier, B. and Jones, N. (2006) Differences in Motivation, Coping Style, and Self-Efficacy among Incarcerated Male and Female Drug Users. *Journal of Substance Abuse Treatment*. [Online]. 30 (2) March, pp. 113–120. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsat.2005.10.006>> [Accessed 18 November 2024].

Petrillo, M. (2021) 'We've All Got a Big Story': Experiences of a Trauma-Informed Intervention in Prison. *The Howard Journal of Crime and Justice*. [Online]. 60 (2) February. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1111/hojo.12408>> [Accessed 9 January 2025].

Pill, N., Day, A. and Mildred, H. (2017) Trauma Responses to Intimate Partner Violence: A Review of Current Knowledge. *Aggression and Violent Behaviour*. [Online]. 34 May, pp. 178–184. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.avb.2017.01.014>> [Accessed 29 October 2024].

Prison Reform Trust (2021) Prison: The Facts. [Online]. Available from: <https://prisonreformtrust.org.uk/wpcontent/uploads/2022/01/Prison_the_facts_2021.pdf> [Accessed 22 November 2024].

Prison Reform Trust (2022) Prison: The Facts. [Online]. Prison Reform Trust. Available from: <<https://prisonreformtrust.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/Prison-the-facts-2022.pdf>> [Accessed 14 January 2025].

Reilly, M. (2024) Effective Trauma-Informed Care That Improves the Psychological Well-Being of Female Inmates: A Systematic Literature Review [Doctoral Thesis]. University of Arizona. Available from: <<https://www.proquest.com/openview/4f0ded89ac3ff5b372da2b5e8d4c345e/1?pqorigsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>> [Accessed 12 January 2025].

Robinson, L. and Forrester, A. (2023) Management of Violence in Prisons. [Online]. In: Khwaja, M. eds., *The Prevention and Management of Violence: Guidance for Mental Healthcare Professionals*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Available from: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=cOC9EAAAQBAJ&dq=underreporting+violence+in+prison&lr=&source=gbs_navlinks_s> [Accessed 22 November 2024].

Ryland, H., Gould, C., McGeorge, T., Hawton, K. and Fazel, S. (2020) Predicting Self-Harm in Prisoners: Risk Factors and a Prognostic Model in a Cohort of 542 Prison Entrants. *European Psychiatry*. [Online]. 63 (1). Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1192/j.eurpsy.2020.40>> [Accessed 21 November 2024].

Schultz, K., Cattaneo, L. B., Sabina, C., Brunner, L., Jackson, S. and Serrata, J. V. (2016) Key Roles of Community Connectedness in Healing from Trauma. *Psychology of Violence*. [Online]. 6 (1), pp. 42–48. Available from: <<http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/vio0000025%20COMMENTARY>> [Accessed 4 February 2025].

Seedat, S., Pienaar, W. P., Williams, D. and Stein, D. J. (2004) Ethics of Research on Survivors of Trauma. *Current Psychiatry Reports*. [Online]. 6 (4) July, pp. 262–267. Available from: <https://scholar.harvard.edu/files/davidrwilliams/files/2004-ethics_of_researchwilliams.pdf> [Accessed 21 February 2025].

Semenza, D. C. and Grosholz, J. M. (2019) Mental and Physical Health in Prison: How CoOccurring Conditions Influence Inmate Misconduct. *Health & Justice*. [Online]. 7 (1) January. Available from: <<https://healthandjusticejournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s40352-018-0082-5>> [Accessed 18 November 2024].

Shammas, V. L. (2017) Pains of Imprisonment. *The Encyclopaedia of Corrections*. [Online]. 1 (1) February, pp. 1–5. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118845387.wbeoc020>> [Accessed 18 November 2024].

Shaw, J. A. (2000) Children, Adolescents and Trauma. *Psychiatric Quarterly*. [Online]. 71 (3), pp. 227–243. Available from: <<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1023/A:1004630127000>> [Accessed 17 October 2024].

Singhal, A., Ross, J., Seminog, O., Hawton, K. and Goldacre, M. J. (2014) Risk of Self-Harm and Suicide in People with Specific Psychiatric and Physical Disorders: Comparisons between Disorders Using English National Record Linkage. *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine*. [Online]. 107 (5) February, pp. 194–204. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/0141076814522033>> [Accessed 19 November 2024].

Snyder, H. (2019) Literature Review as a Research Methodology: An Overview and Guidelines. *Journal of Business Research*. [Online]. 104 (1), pp. 333–339. Available from: <<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0148296319304564>> [Accessed 21 February 2025].

Sobočan, A. M., Bertotti, T. and Strom-Gottfried, K. (2019) Ethical Considerations in Social Work Research. *European Journal of Social Work*. [Online]. 22 (5) November, pp. 1–14. Available from: <<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/13691457.2018.1544117>> [Accessed 21 February 2025].

Sorensen, J. R., Cunningham, M. D., Vigen, M. P. and Woods, S. O. (2011) Serious Assaults on Prison Staff: A Descriptive Analysis. *Journal of Criminal Justice*. [Online]. 39 (2) March, pp. 143–150. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcrimjus.2011.01.002>> [Accessed 29 November 2024].

Sousa, M., Gonçalves, R. A., Cruz, A. R. and Castro Rodrigues, A. (2019) Prison Officers' Attitudes towards Self-Harm in Prisoners. *International Journal of Law and Psychiatry*. [Online]. 66 (1) September, p. 101490. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijlp.2019.101490>> [Accessed 21 November 2024].

Spencer, D. C., Ricciardelli, R. and Dodge, A. (2020) 'Society Wants to See a True Victim': Police Interpretations of Victims of Sexual Violence. *Feminist Criminology*. [Online]. 16 (2) November, p.

155708512097027. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/1557085120970270>> [Accessed 29 October 2024].

Statham, B. M., Winder, B. and Micklethwaite, D. (2020) Success within a UK Open Prison and Surviving the 'Pains of Freedom'. *Psychology, Crime & Law*. [Online]. 27 (8) November, pp. 1–22. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/1068316X.2020.1849697>> [Accessed 30 January 2025].

Steiner, B. and Wooldredge, J. (2016) Individual and Environmental Influences on Prison Officer Safety. *Justice Quarterly*. [Online]. 34 (2) March, pp. 324–349. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/07418825.2016.1164883>> [Accessed 26 November 2024].

Stoliker, B. E. (2016) Inmate Mental Health Predicting the Likelihood of Physical and Verbal Assault on Correctional Staff. *Journal for Social Thought*. [Online]. 1 (1) July. Available from: <<https://ojs.lib.uwo.ca/index.php/jst/article/view/495/282>> [Accessed 27 November 2024].

Struckman-Johnson, C. and Struckman-Johnson, D. (2000) Sexual Coercion Rates in Seven Midwestern Prison Facilities for Men. *The Prison Journal*. [Online]. 80 (4) December, pp. 379–390. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/0032885500080004004>> [Accessed 22 November 2024].

Sturge, G. (2024) UK Prison Population Statistics. [Online]. Parliament.uk. Available from: <<https://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/SN04334/SN04334.pdf>> [Accessed 14 January 2025].

Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration (SAMHSA) (2014a) SAMHSA's Concept of Trauma and Guidance for a Trauma-Informed Approach. [Online]. Available from: <<https://library.samhsa.gov/sites/default/files/sma14-4884.pdf>> [Accessed 14 January 2025].

Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration (SAMHSA) (2014b) Trauma-Informed Care in Behavioral Health Services TIP 57. [Online]. Rockville, MD: Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration. Available from: <<https://library.samhsa.gov/sites/default/files/sma14-4816.pdf>> [Accessed 30 January 2025].

Suri, H. (2020) Ethical Considerations of Conducting Systematic Reviews in Educational Research. *Systematic Reviews in Educational Research*. [Online]. 1 (1), pp. 41–54. Available from: <https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-658-27602-7_3> [Accessed 21 February 2025].

Suto, I. and Arnaut, G. L. Y. (2010) Suicide in Prison: A Qualitative Study. *The Prison Journal*. [Online]. 90 (3) July, pp. 288–312. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/0032885510373499>> [Accessed 22 November 2024].

The National Child Traumatic Stress Network (2008) Making the Connection: Trauma and Substance Abuse. [Online]. Available from: <https://www.nctsn.org/sites/default/files/resources/making_the_connection_trauma_substance_abuse.pdf> [Accessed 13 January 2025].

Towl, G. J., Crighton, D. A. and Toharris (2017) *Suicide in Prisons: Prisoners' Lives Matter*. [Online]. Hook, Hampshire: Waterside Press. Available from: <<https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/leedsbeck/reader.action?docID=4856380>> [Accessed 22 November 2024].

Treisman, K. (2021) *Treasure Box For Creating Trauma-Informed Organizations: A Ready-ToUse Resource For... Trauma, Adversity, and Culturally Informed, Infuse*. [Online]. S.L.: Jessica Kingsley. Available from: <<https://r3.vlereader.com/EpubReader?ean=1781839971365#>> [Accessed 9 January 2025].

Ugelvik, T. (2014) Paternal Pains of Imprisonment: Incarcerated Fathers, Ethnic Minority Masculinity and Resistance Narratives. *Punishment & Society*. [Online]. 16 (2) March, pp. 152–168. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/1462474513517020>> [Accessed 20 January 2025].

Uglean, T. M. (2024) The Need for States to Implement Trauma-Informed Care Policies. [Online]. Clark Digital Commons. Available from: <https://commons.clarku.edu/graduate_school_professional_studies/21> [Accessed 14 January 2025].

Van Beeck, M., Bogaerts, S., Sellbom, M., Somma, A., Fossati, A., Brehmer, Y., Jankovic, M. and Garofalo, C. (2024) The Relationship between Experiencing Childhood Trauma and Psychopathic Personality Traits: The Mediating Role of Insecure Attachment. *Journal of Aggression Maltreatment & Trauma*. [Online]. 33 (9) July, pp. 1–18. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/10926771.2024.2381558>> [Accessed 8 October 2024].

Vaswani, N. and Paul, S. (2019) 'It's Knowing the Right Things to Say and Do': Challenges and Opportunities for Trauma-Informed Practice in the Prison Context. *The Howard Journal of Crime and Justice*. [Online]. 58 (4) September, pp. 513–534. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1111/hojo.12344>> [Accessed 5 January 2025].

Waite, S. (2023a) 'Their Ethos Is All about Building Trust': An Exploration of Staff-Prisoner Relationships at a Women's Open Prison [Thesis]. Leeds Beckett University. Available from: <https://figshare.leedsbeckett.ac.uk/articles/thesis/Their%20ethos%20is%20all%20about%20_%20_%20_%20_%20_%20_%20building_%20trust%20An%20_%20of%20StaffPrisoner%20Relationships%20at%20a%20Women%20s%20Open%20Prison/22268983/1> [Accessed 29 January 2025].

Waite, S. (2023b) Imprisoned Women's Experiences Of Trust In Staff-Prisoner Relationships In An English Open Prison. [Online]. In: Masson, I. and Booth, N. eds., *The Routledge handbook of women's experiences of criminal justice*. New York: Taylor & Francis Group. Available from: <<https://www-taylorfrancis-com.leedsbeckett.idm.oclc.org/books/edit/10.4324/9781003202295/routledge-handbookwomen-experiences-criminal-justice- isla-masson-natalie-booth>> [Accessed 12 January 2025].

Waite, S. (2024) Mapping the Landscape of Trust: Towards a Typology in the Context of the Prison - Leeds Beckett Repository. *Leedsbeckett.ac.uk*. [Online], (275) October. Available from: <<https://eprints.leedsbeckett.ac.uk/id/eprint/11342/>> [Accessed 29 January 2025].

Witt, A., Sachser, C., Plener, P. L., Brähler, E. and Fegert, J. M. (2019) The Prevalence and Consequences of Adverse Childhood Experiences in the German Population. *Deutsches Aerzteblatt Online*. [Online]. 116 (38) September. Available from: <<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6829158/>> [Accessed 31 January 2025].

Wittbrodt, M. T., Vaccarino, V., Shah, A. J., Mayer, E. A. and Bremner, J. D. (2020) Psychometric Properties of the Adulthood Trauma Inventory. *Health Psychology*. [Online]. 39 (8) August, pp. 679–688. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1037/hea0000856>> [Accessed 18 October 2024].

Wolff, N., Blitz, C. L., Shi, J., Bachman, R. and Siegel, J. A. (2006) Sexual Violence inside Prisons: Rates of Victimization. *Journal of Urban Health*. [Online]. 83 (5) May, pp. 835–848. Available from: <<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11524-006-9065-2>> [Accessed 22 November 2024].

Wolff, N., Blitz, C. L., Shi, J., Siegel, J. and Bachman, R. (2007) Physical Violence inside Prisons. *Criminal Justice and Behaviour*. [Online], 34 (5) April, pp. 588–599. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1177/0093854806296830>> [Accessed 22 November 2024].

Wolff, N., Shi, J. and Siegel, J. (2009) Understanding Physical Victimization inside Prisons: Factors That Predict Risk. *Justice Quarterly*. [Online]. 26 (3) September, pp. 445–475. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/07418820802427858>> [Accessed 22 November 2024].

Wooldredge, J. (2020) Prison Culture, Management, and In-Prison Violence. *Annual Review of Criminology* [Online], 3 (1) January, pp. 165–188. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-criminol-011419-041359>> [Accessed 27 November 2024].

Wortley, R. (2002) *Situational Prison Control: Crime Prevention in Correctional Institutions*. [Online]. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Available from: <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=Uxe1_tkxtt4C&dq=Situational+prison+control:+Crime+prevention+in+correctional+institutions&lr=&source=gbs_navlinks_s> [Accessed 27 November 2024].

Wright, K. and Laurent, N. (2021) Safety, Collaboration, and Empowerment. *Archivaria*. [Online]. 91 (91) June, pp. 38–73. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.7202/1078465ar>> [Accessed 3 February 2025].

Zhang, A. (2022) The Failure of Ganhua Education: Revisiting Relational-Cultural Theory in China's Female Prisons. *Women & Criminal Justice*. [Online]. 34 (5) February, pp. 1–19. Available from: <<https://doi.org/10.1080/08974454.2022.2040694>> [Accessed 7 January 2025].

Zhong, S., Senior, M., Yu, R., Perry, A., Hawton, K., Shaw, J. and Fazel, S. (2021) Risk Factors for Suicide in Prisons: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *The Lancet Public Health*. [Online]. 6 (3) February. Available from: <<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2468266720302334>> [Accessed 22 November 2024].